

THE INDUS ELEPHANT SEALS

The Royal Terminology of The Indus Valley Civilization

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Abstract

This study presents an analysis and interpretation of all known Indus texts featuring the elephant motif, contextualized within the framework of the Sindhu Alphabet. A corpus of 29 seals from the Indus Valley Civilization, depicting the elephant, was analysed using the Corpus of Indus Seals and Inscriptions: Collections in Pakistan and India. Drawing upon an extensive review of Vedic texts, Sanskrit dictionaries, and other relevant scriptures, plausible meanings and interpretations for the associated inscriptions are proposed. These texts appear to convey royal terminology, encompassing titles, tribal identities, and aspects of administrative and clerical practices. This research aims to serve as a valuable resource for scholars, providing a foundation for further validation or constructive critique.

Introduction

Interpreting a 5,000-year-old language with a documented record spanning more than seven centuries presents an exceedingly challenging task. This endeavor requires addressing its multifaceted aspects, including linguistic, chronological, archaeological, genetic, anthropological, religious, and traditional dimensions. To this end, I have been actively seeking collaboration with experts across these diverse fields to refine my findings and validate my proposed Indus alphabet. While I have received encouragement from many senior scholars, I recognize that some reservations persist within the academic community. Limited resources and the inherently complex nature of this ambitious undertaking may prolong the process; nonetheless, I remain both optimistic and patient. Meanwhile, I continue to share new insights and perspectives, welcoming constructive feedback and thoughtful guidance.

This and subsequent papers focus primarily on the application of the proposed alphabet and the exploration of its strict linguistic rules. The central question driving this work is: What insights do the Indus texts offer in light of the proposed Indus alphabet? My analysis seeks to incorporate all relevant perspectives and interpretations concerning the decipherment of these texts. With over 4,000 extant Indus texts available, I have chosen to commence my study with those featuring elephant motifs. These particular inscriptions suggest a strong connection to royal terminology and the clerical aspects of the era. The elephant, as depicted in the texts, emerges as a powerful symbol of authority, representing the ruling class and the concept of emperorship within the social and political hierarchy of the Indus Valley Civilization.

The primary objective of this research is to explore the linguistic validation of the proposed alphabet—a critical step toward identifying the language of the Indus Valley Civilization. I encourage scholars from related disciplines to further investigate these findings.

While notable progress has been made in interpreting the Indus texts, this work does not fully address the broader historical and cultural dimensions of the inscriptions.

One noteworthy aspect of the elephant motifs is their distinct artistic execution, marked by unique design elements and aesthetic considerations. To illustrate this, the analysis includes two seals featuring elephant motifs as examples. The inscribed texts on these seals exhibit cypher-like qualities. When read in parts or even as whole words, the inscriptions maintain contextual coherence, suggesting an intentional embedding of multiple layers of meaning and interpretation. These inscriptions offer a wealth of representational possibilities and demand careful analysis to uncover their significance.

The Sindhu Alphabet

Vowels: Table:01

ao	اَو	o	او	ae	اَي	e	اي	ū	اُو	u	اُ	ī	اِي	i	اِ	ā	آ	a	اَ
⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘

Semi-vowels: Table:02

Base sign with Semi-vowels and nasal	Nasal and Semi-Vowel	Pronunciation of modified letter		Nasal and Semi-Vowels
⌘	,	mañ	مان	ن
⌘		mṛ	مري	ر
⌘	┆	lṛ	لر	ر
⌘	⌘	ḍra	ڊر	ر
⌘	⌘	pl	پل	ل

Consonants: Table:03

jh	جه	j	ج	p	پ	ṭh	ٹ	t	ت	th	ث	t	ت	bh	پ	ḅ	ب	b	ب
⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘
ḍ	ڊ	ḍ	ڊ	dh	ڌ	d	د	kh	خ	h	ح	chh	چ	ch	چ	jñ	ج	ḅ	ب
⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘
q	ق	ph	ف	f	ف	v	ع	sh	ش	s	س	z	ز	ṭ	ژ	r	ر	ḍh	ڊ
⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘	⌘

ṇ	ṅ	n	ṇ	m	ṃ	l	ḷ	gn	ग	gh	ग	ḡ	ḡ	g	ग	kh	क	k	क	
				人	人	∪	∪													
						aspirate	وسرگ	ś	ش	y	ي	v	و	h	ه	v	و			
						∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧

1. The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-282

Figure: 01

Table: 04

𑀧𑀭𑀸𑀓	𑀧𑀭𑀸𑀓	𑀧𑀭𑀸𑀓	𑀧𑀭𑀸𑀓	𑀧𑀭𑀸𑀓	𑀧𑀭𑀸𑀓	𑀧𑀭𑀸𑀓	𑀧𑀭𑀸𑀓	𑀧𑀭𑀸𑀓	𑀧𑀭𑀸𑀓
(P-04)	(P-33)	(P-214)	(P-376)	Pati	𑀧𑀭𑀸𑀓 (P13+147)	q/k	t	Pati Makuta	
					m+a				

For detailed information about the first sign reading ‘Pati,’ it is important to note that the Indus Script, unlike Sanskrit and other Prakritic ancient alphabets, has distinct sounds for ‘k’ and ‘q.’ For further analysis concerning this variation and the representation of the sign ‘Pati’ and the ‘k’ sound, please refer to "The Alphabet of Sindhu Prakrit" (Muhammad M H, 2023).

Iconographic Elements Possess Symbolic Features

Figure: 02

i) The Crown Having Three Points

Makuṭa or Makutāgama refers to one of the twenty-eight Siddhāntāgama: a classification of the Śaiva division of Śaivāgamas. The Śaivāgamas represent the wisdom that has come down from lord Śiva, received by Pārvatī and accepted by Viṣṇu.

The term *mukuṭa* (also spelled *makuṭa*) refers to a crown, diadem, or tiara, often described as crescent-shaped in contrast to other headgear like the *kirīṭa*, which is pointed, and the *mauli*, which has three points. It can also denote a crest, peak, or point, and in some contexts, it serves as a proper noun, particularly in reference to places or individuals (derived from *Rāja-mukuṭa*).

In Sanskrit and Pali dictionaries, *makuṭa* is consistently defined as a type of crown or head-dress. In the *Practical Sanskrit-English Dictionary*, *makuṭa* is described as a crown, and similar definitions are found in the *Cologne Digital Sanskrit Dictionaries*, where it is listed as a crest, crown, or tiara. The *BuddhaSasana* dictionary further supports this interpretation, identifying *makuṭa* as a crest or coronet. Additionally, in Pali texts like the *Abhidhamma Piṭaka*, *makuṭa* is mentioned as a crest, often alongside *kirīṭa*, emphasizing its role as an adornment.

Beyond its general meaning, *makuṭa* also holds a specific place in Śaiva iconography. According to the *Śaivāgamas*, *makuṭa* refers to one of the twenty-eight *Siddhāntāgamas*, a division within the Śaiva tradition of sacred texts. These *Śaivāgamas* are believed to contain wisdom transmitted from Lord Śiva to Pārvatī, and later accepted by Viṣṇu, reinforcing the spiritual significance of *makuṭa* in Shaivism.

Figure: 03

ii) The Intriguing Fish Sign (P-60)

A meticulous examination of the iconography on seal M-282 reveals a curious detail: a diminutive fish sign (P-60) inscribed where the elephant's eye would typically be located. Deciphering the meaning behind this unconventional substitution is of particular interest. Let's examine the meaning of this sign:

Table: 05

 (P- 60)	Sa / Śa
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Figure: 04

In the practical Sanskrit-English dictionary, the term "Śa" (श) is defined as follows:

Cutter or Destroyer: This refers to someone or something that cuts or destroys, which could symbolize a powerful or destructive force.

A Weapon: The word also denotes an instrument or tool of destruction, typically a weapon.

Name of Śiva: "Śa" is also used as a name for the Hindu deity Śiva, who is known as the destroyer in the Trimurti (the trinity of supreme divinity in Hinduism). This usage likely relates to Śiva's association with destruction and transformation, fitting the earlier meanings of a cutter or destroyer.

iii) Unconventional Trunk

The trunk in this motif does not display a conventional appearance; instead, it represents an ancient war weapon. This is further elucidated by the sign replaced with the eye of the elephant.

2. The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-283

Figure:05

Table:06

Ψ	 	Ψ
P-91	P-135	Vagga
v	gg	

In the realm of ancient linguistic traditions, the term *vagga* or its Sanskrit equivalent *varga* carries a range of meanings rooted in the concepts of grouping and categorization. Let us explore its various interpretations and usages across Pali and Sanskrit. In Sindhi this term is existed as 'Vaagga'. It may be the earliest form of term rule or govern.

Origin and Basic Meaning

The word *vagga* in Pali, derived from the Vedic root *vrj*, is often translated as a "group," "party," or "section." In Sanskrit, the term appears as *varga*, a word that similarly connotes a collection or classification of entities, animate or inanimate. Both forms share an etymological connection with the Latin *volgus* or *vulgus*, meaning "crowd" or "common people," which also gave rise to the English word "vulgar." In my opinion the English word 'govern' also related to this root.

Detailed Definitions Across Textual Sources

1. Pali Contexts:

In Pali dictionaries like *BuddhaSasana's Concise Pali-English Dictionary* and the *Pali Text Society's Dictionary*, *vagga* signifies a group or party, often used in Buddhist texts to denote sections of a discourse or a collective of individuals sharing common characteristics.

2. Sanskrit Interpretations:

The Sanskrit term *varga* is deeply rooted in classical texts and philosophical treatises. It primarily refers to a class or division, encompassing various forms of categorization:

- A **group or company** of similar things: This usage is seen in poetic and narrative literature, such as the *Kumārasambhava* and the *Pañcatantra*. For example, *nakṣatravarga* refers to a collection of stars, while *pauravarga* denotes a group of city-dwellers.
- A **party or side**: In contexts of alliances or opposing forces, *varga* denotes a faction or side in a larger conflict, as exemplified in classical epics and dramas.
- A **category or sphere**: Philosophical and scientific texts use the term to group concepts, such as *dharma*, *artha*, and *kāma*, which encompass the pursuits of worldly existence.
- **Strength or power**: In some contexts, such as the *Naighaṇṭuka*, *varga* signifies strength, emphasizing its metaphorical usage.

3. Specialized Meanings and Applications:

- In the *Varāha-mihira's Brhat-saṃhitā*, *varga* is used to denote everything comprehended under a particular department or sphere, illustrating its application in categorizing celestial and earthly phenomena.
- In Buddhist literature, *varga* also appears as the name of a country, reflecting its geographical or cultural connotation in specific contexts.

3. *The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-278*

Figure: 06

Table:07

P-270+ Slanty Diacritic mark	P-91	P-131	P-127	P-376	Ni Vaga ta
ni	v	g	a	t	

The Sanskrit term "Ni" is a versatile prefix with a broad range of applications in verbs, nouns, and occasionally as an adverb.

General Overview

The prefix "Ni" serves as a modifier that conveys various shades of meaning depending on the context. It is primarily used to emphasize concepts of **direction, state, action, or quality**. This makes it an integral component in constructing nuanced meanings in Sanskrit words and phrases.

Primary Meanings

1. **Downward Motion or Lowness**
 - Often used to indicate something moving down, being under, or situated below.
 - Example: *Nipat* (falling down), *Niṣad* (sitting down).
2. **Collection or Grouping**
 - Represents a gathering or a collection.
 - Example: *Nikāya* (assembly), *Nikara* (mass).
3. **Intensity**
 - Denotes an increased degree or intensity of an action or state.
 - Example: *Nikāma* (intensely desired), *Nigrhīta* (severely restrained).
4. **Order or Command**
 - Used in contexts implying direction, instruction, or authority.
 - Example: *Nideśaḥ* (command, directive).
5. **Continuance or Permanence**
 - Implies persistence or something enduring over time.
 - Example: *Niviśate* (settling down permanently).
6. **Skill or Expertise**
 - Associated with proficiency or mastery in a particular field.
 - Example: *Nipūṇa* (skilled, expert).
7. **Restraint or Confinement**
 - Indicates restriction or control, either physically or metaphorically.
 - Example: *Nibandha* (binding, restriction).
8. **Inclusion**
 - Suggests an idea of being "into" or "within."
 - Example: *Nipītamudakam* (water consumed or absorbed).
9. **Certainty and Affirmation**
 - Conveys emphasis on assurance or decisiveness.

○

Applications in Contexts

- **Ritualistic Actions:** In phrases like *Nimicchati* or *Nirmicchati*, "Ni" is used to describe ceremonial acts like the auspicious waving of lights around a deity or person, signifying reverence or blessings.
- **Leadership and Guidance:** When used in nouns like *Nī* (नी), it denotes a leader or guide, as seen in *Grāmañī* (village leader) or *Senāñī* (army leader).
- **Transformation and Reduction:** Indicates reducing someone or something to a particular state, e.g., *Vaśam nī* (to bring under control), *Bhasmasāt nī* (to turn into ashes).
- **Investigation and Decision:** Implies thorough inquiry or resolution of a matter, e.g., *Vyavahārān naya* (deciding a case or legal matter).

Ta:

The word *Tā* holds profound significance in the Sanskrit language, embodying a range of meanings that highlight its versatility and depth. At its core, *Tā* signifies **excellence** or **eminence**, denoting a sense of greatness or superiority. This interpretation often aligns with qualities of distinction or exceptional virtue, making the term a descriptor for what is outstanding or noteworthy.

In another context, *Tā* refers to the **hip** or **flank**, a physical connotation that may be used in poetic or descriptive language, emphasizing the graceful and delicate parts of the human body. Beyond the anatomical reference, the term also finds resonance in the world of valor, signifying a **warrior** — someone who embodies courage, strength, and discipline on the battlefield.

Delving further, *Tā* represents **virtue** or **religious merit**, underscoring its connection to spirituality and moral values. This usage reflects the importance of righteousness and dharma in Sanskrit literature and philosophy.

Lastly, in mythology, *Tā* is also the name of **Lakṣmī**, the goddess of wealth, prosperity, and fortune. This divine association enhances the term's cultural and religious significance, portraying it as a symbol of grace and abundance.

4. The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-279

Figure: 07

Table:08

△	⊙	𑀓	𑀅	U	△⊙𑀓𑀅U
P-189	P-60	P-101+147	P-127	P-296	ṭha saka pa
ṭh	s	ka	a	p	

Ṭha: The term "Ṭha" (𑀅), as described in various Sanskrit-English dictionaries, has several meanings and applications:

1. It is described as an **imitative sound**, resembling the noise of a metallic jar or a golden pitcher rolling down steps. This is often depicted with expressions like *ṭhaṭhaṃ ṭhaṭhaṃ ṭhaṃ ṭhaṭhaṃ* in literary sources such as the *Mahānāṭaka*.
2. The term also denotes a **loud noise**, emphasizing its auditory connotations.
3. It represents a **circle or a globe**, as well as the **disk of the sun or the moon**, signifying celestial or geometric forms.
4. "Ṭha" is used as a **cypher (zero)**, a symbol of mathematical abstraction.
5. It refers to an **object of sense**, possibly alluding to tangible or perceivable entities.
6. Another meaning is a **place frequented by all** or **held sacred**, suggesting a location of common gathering or religious importance.
7. The term is used for an **idol or deity**, underscoring its connection to worship and sacred representations.
8. "Ṭha" is also an epithet of **Śiva**, aligning it with divine significance in Hindu theology.

Saka: The term "Śāka" or "Śāka" (शाक/शक) encompasses a wide range of meanings and historical associations across Sanskrit literature, Puranic texts, and historical references. These interpretations highlight its cultural, geographical, and mythological significance:

1. Śāka in the Varāha-purāṇa

- **Rajata Mountain:** Śāka is another name for *Rajata*, one of the seven major mountains in Śākadvīpa as described in Chapter 86 of the *Varāha-purāṇa*.
- **Śākadvīpa:** This is one of the seven islands (*dvīpa*) governed by Medhātithi, a son of Priyavrata, who was himself the son of Svāyambhuva Manu.

2. Śāka in the Mahābhārata and Puranic Texts

- **People and Tribes:**
 - The Śakas are a particular tribe or caste mentioned prominently in the *Mahābhārata*.
 - They participated in Yudhiṣṭhira's *Rājasūya yajña* (*Sabhā Parva*, Chapter 51, Verse 32).
 - Originally *Kṣatriyas*, the Śakas were demoted to *Śūdras* due to the displeasure of Brahmins (*Anuśāsana Parva*, Chapter 33, Verse 21).
 - They allied with the Yavanas to aid the Haihaya kings against Paraśurāma.
- **Northern Kingdom:**
 - The Śakas are referred to as a northern kingdom, contemporaneous with the Śiśunāgas. They ruled for 380 years (according to the *Vāyu-purāṇa*), and were said to be conquered by Kalki in the future.
- **Geographical Connection:**
 - In Buddhist texts like the *Mahāsaṃnipāta-sūtra* (*Candragarbha*), Śāka is associated with Śravaṇānakṣatra, where the Nakṣatras were entrusted with the protection of kingdoms such as Śāka.

3. Historical Interpretations

- **Scythians and Migrations:**
 - The Śakas are equated with the Scythians, known for their migrations from Bactria and Gandhara to Eastern Europe and Northern Anatolia around 3100-3000 BCE.
 - The Scythians are believed to have introduced the worship of Vedic gods like Mithra, Indra, and Varuṇa in the west, evolving into Mithraism.
- **Mudrārākṣasa Context:**

- The *Mudrārākṣasa* mentions Śaka as one of the tribal territories, situated along the river Cakṣu (Amu Darya or Oxus), as per Purāṇic lists.

4. Etymological and Symbolic Associations

- **Śaka as an Era:**

- Śaka refers to an era, particularly associated with King Śālivāhana. The Śaka era begins in 78 CE, often used in historical and calendrical contexts.
- The term *Śaka-swaras* denotes eras named after prominent rulers like Yudhiṣṭhira, Vikramāditya, and Śālivāhana.

- **Mythological Connections:**

- The Śakas are one of the seven *Dvīpas* or world divisions, particularly the sixth, surrounded by the *Kṣīroda-samudra* (sea of milk).
- Śaka also signifies strength and power, symbolized by the *Śirīṣa tree* (*Acacia sirisa*) and the teak tree (*Tectona grandis*).

5. Dictionaries and Lexicons

- **Śaka in Lexicography:**

- The term denotes a sovereign or prince who gives their name to an era.
- It refers to a particular caste, a country, the inhabitants of that country (Sacæ or Scythians), and an era.

Here are two further examples of Indus Texts of the same type from the Mahadevan's Book.

4448 (10) (ka+pala+ sakka)

The religion of the early Iranians of the Saka branch, who migrated to Central Asia around 1500 BCE, is closely tied to linguistic insights. According to Asko Parpola, the Proto-Saka term *dasa, meaning "man," serves as the etymological root for the ethnic name Dahanu found in Old Persian. This aligns with a broader pattern where many ethnic self-designations derive from words meaning "man." For example, the native ethnic name of the Mari, speakers of a Uralic (Finno-Ugric) language, originates from the Proto-Indo-Aryan term *marya-, which means "man" or "mortal" (literally "one who has to die").

I mention here another Text which indicates the ethnic name of the Mari of Saka branch:

1117 (00) (pati+ mri+ sakka)

Pā: The Sanskrit term "Pā" and its related derivatives carry nuanced meanings that span across protection, governance, and preservation, while also encompassing the act of drinking in

specific contexts. Below is an academic narrative detailing the diverse usages of "Pā" and its related forms as found in traditional Sanskrit dictionaries:

The root **Pā** classified in both the first (pibati) and second (pāti) conjugations, embodies meanings central to guarding, protecting, preserving, and nourishing. It also signifies the act of drinking when derived in the first conjugation. This multifaceted root permeates various lexical and grammatical constructions, often nuanced by context.

1. Protecting, Guarding, and Preserving

The primary and most significant interpretation of "Pā" revolves around protection and preservation. Classical texts frequently employ this term to describe the safeguarding of people, principles, or entities. For example, in **Raghuvamśa (1.25)**, the phrase *paryāpto'si prajāḥ pātum* illustrates a ruler's sufficiency in protecting his subjects. Similarly, in **Mṛcchakaṭīka (1.61)**, the governing responsibility is emphasized with the expression *pāntu pṛthvīm...bhūpāḥ*, invoking the duty of kings to rule and protect the earth.

2. Ruling and Governing

The connotation of "Pā" as governance extends naturally from its protective implications. The term is commonly associated with rulers or sovereigns who are entrusted with the welfare of their dominion. Titles like **nṛpa** (protector of men) and **kṣitīpa** (protector of the earth) derive from this root, signifying their role as custodians of order and justice.

3. Observing and Noticing

In Vedic contexts, "Pā" also signifies observation and attention, suggesting an active awareness or mindfulness. This interpretation reflects the root's broader sense of care and attentiveness.

4. Derivatives and Compound Forms

Derivatives of "Pā" include:

- **Gopa**: A protector or keeper, especially a cowherd.
- **Dvārpa**: A doorkeeper, denoting one who guards a door.
- **Kṣitīpa**: A king or ruler, highlighting the role of guardianship over the earth.

In compounds, the suffix "-pa" often implies drinking, guarding, or ruling, as in **pāda-pa** (tree, literally "drinking through its roots") or **daśapa** (a governor of ten villages).

5. Causal and Extended Meanings

The causative form **pālayati** deepens the root's applicability, denoting actions such as protecting, governing, adhering to vows, bringing up, or even awaiting something. For instance, **Manusmṛti (9.18)** illustrates the role of a ruler in upholding dharma with *katham duṣṭhuḥ svayaṁ dharme prajāś tvam pālayisyasi*. Here, "pālayisyasi" underscores the act of ethical governance.

7. Symbolic Extensions

Metaphorical uses of "Pā" extend its protective essence to abstract realms such as cherishing and fulfilling duties or vows. For example, **Raghuvamśa (13.65)** describes the fulfillment of a promise with *pālitasaṅgarāya*.

5. The Inscribed Texts on Seal H-91

Figure: 08

Figure: 09

Table:09

△	†	ℓ	ṽ	⋈	△	†	ℓ	ṽ	⋈	△†ℓṽ⋈
P-189	P-120	P-168	P-126	P-261	ṭh	m̄	s/s̄	ṛ:	ṭṭ	ṭhamaśṭṭra

‘Thamastra’ Unconventional Colour of The Seal Indicates the Darkness

In the rich tapestry of Indian philosophy and literature, the concept of *Tamas* is woven into various texts, each offering a nuanced understanding of this profound idea. At its core,

Tamas is one of the three *guṇas* or fundamental qualities that pervade the universe, as explored in the Dharma-śāstra literature, including the Manusmṛti. These *guṇas*—*Sattva* (purity), *Rajas* (passion), and *Tamas* (ignorance)—are said to shape the nature and behavior of all beings, influencing their actions and thoughts.

In the context of the *Bṛihat Samhita* by Varahamihira, *Tamas* is portrayed as the primordial darkness, the chaos that predates creation. It symbolizes the state of confusion and unmanifest potential before the cosmos takes form. This association with darkness is further elaborated in the *Shiva Purana*, where *Tamas* is described as an inherent part of the cosmic illusion, *avidyā*, which manifests during Brahmā's creative process.

The *Puranic Encyclopedia* provides a different lens, identifying *Tamas* as a hell, a realm of suffering and gloom. This interpretation aligns with the more psychological and moral dimensions of *Tamas* described in various Sanskrit dictionaries. Here, *Tamas* is not only the darkness of the mind—encompassing ignorance, illusion, and error—but also the source of negative emotions and behaviors such as anger, greed, and sorrow.

In Ayurveda, *Tamas* is recognized as a quality of the mind that leads to delusion and ignorance, hindering spiritual progress and clarity. The *Practical Sanskrit-English Dictionary* and other lexicons further reinforce this idea, associating *Tamas* with mental blindness and worldly delusion, which cloud the mind and lead to sin and grief.

Interestingly, the concept of *Tamas* also touches upon celestial phenomena, with some Sanskrit dictionaries attributing the darkness of solar and lunar eclipses to the influence of *Rāhu*, a mythical demon. This symbolic intertwining of cosmic and psychological darkness illustrates the pervasive nature of *Tamas* in the Indian worldview, where it is seen as both a physical and metaphysical force.

Thus, across various texts and traditions, *Tamas* emerges as a multifaceted concept, representing ignorance, darkness, and the chaotic forces that challenge the clarity of mind and spirit. It is a reminder of the dualities within the universe and the ongoing struggle to transcend the veils of illusion and reach a state of enlightenment.

6. *The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-286*

Figure: 10

Table:10

ॐ	ॐ	ॐ	ॐ ॐ ॐ
P-311	P-83	P-302	Pā śamba
p	śam̐	b	

The name *Samba* and its variations, including *Śamba*, *Sāmba*, and *Ṣamba*, carry a rich tapestry of meanings and mythological significance within Hindu traditions and Sanskrit literature. Each interpretation and context add layers of depth to these terms, weaving together themes of joy, misfortune, weaponry, and divine lore.

Samba in Mythology

Samba is best known as a prominent figure in Hindu mythology. He is a Yadava prince, the son of Lord Krishna and Jāmbavatī. A tale recounts how Samba once disguised himself as a woman and, through a sequence of events foretold by sages, became the bearer of a calamitous iron mace. This weapon, destined to bring destruction, ultimately led to the downfall of the Yadava clan, fulfilling the curse of the rishis. The myth paints Samba as both a central and tragic figure, embodying themes of destiny, divine retribution, and cosmic cycles.

Śamba: Interpretations and Symbolism

The term *Śamba* holds dual and seemingly contradictory meanings. It can signify being *happy* and *fortunate*, encapsulating joy and prosperity. Yet, it also represents being *poor* or *unfortunate*, revealing the spectrum of human experience. These meanings suggest that *Śamba* transcends material conditions, symbolizing the dualities of life.

In physical and martial contexts, *Śamba* refers to powerful tools and implements. It is identified as:

1. **Indra's thunderbolt** (*vajra*), a celestial weapon symbolizing power and divine authority.
2. The **iron head of a pestle**, a tool of labor and destruction.
3. An **iron chain worn around the loins**, perhaps a symbol of bondage or strength.

Additionally, *Śamba* is linked to agricultural practices, representing the **second ploughing of a field**, tying the term to cycles of cultivation and growth.

Sāmba: Divine Associations

The variant *Sāmba* has a strong association with divinity, particularly as a name of Lord Śiva, one of the principal deities of Hinduism. The term also signifies being “attended by *Ambā*” (a form of Goddess Pārvatī), linking it to themes of companionship and divine feminine energy.

In another notable interpretation, *Sāmba* refers to a prince cursed to produce an iron club for the destruction of his lineage. This tale emphasizes the inescapable nature of fate, even for the divine.

Linguistic Roots and Variants

From a linguistic standpoint, *Śamba* and related terms derive from roots that connote happiness (*śam*) or accumulation (*śamb*). Variants like *Ṣamba* and *Sāmba* expand the meanings to include actions like assembling, uniting, or joining, emphasizing themes of togetherness and creation.

Śamba in Historical and Literary Contexts

In ancient texts, *Śamba* is referenced as a specific weapon used by Indra, underscoring its importance in Vedic warfare and mythology. It also appears as the name of an asura (demon), highlighting its versatility in characterizing both divine and malevolent forces.

7. The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-285

Figure: 11

Table:11

P-193	P-97	P-72	P-127	P-376	ayataṇa sidha
Ā+yy	t/a+ṇ	ś	a	dh	

The sign P-97 is a compound sign, with its lower component resembling sign P-361. However, its general behavior as a vowel sign differs significantly in its frequent usage. Based on this variation, its sound may correspond more closely to that of sign P-376. For further explanation, refer to seal M-1159. Consequently, both possible readings are provided.

On the other hand, sign P-72 lacks an edge on the upper right side, suggesting that the left edge might serve as a diacritic mark. Alternatively, its other possible reading could be Śadha or Sanskrit form Śradha.

Āyatana: In the vast domain of Sanskrit vocabulary, the term *Āyatana* carries a rich array of meanings, each imbued with its own depth and context. Derived from the root "āyata" meaning "to extend" or "to stretch out," combined with the suffix "lyut," the term broadly signifies a place of rest, abode, or support.

Primary Meanings and Contextual Usage:

1. Abode or Resting Place:

At its core, *Āyatana* refers to a place where one resides or rests. This meaning encompasses homes, houses, or any form of dwelling that provides shelter and a sense of permanence. Ancient texts like the *Taittirīya-saṃhitā* and *Chāndogya Upaniṣad* often use this term in the context of a spiritual or physical abode.

2. Sacred Fire and Altar:

In Vedic and ritualistic contexts, *Āyatana* denotes the designated place for sacred fire (*agny-āyatana*). It serves as the seat of sacrificial offerings and plays a pivotal role in various ceremonies. Texts like the *Āśvalāyana-śrauta-sūtra* detail its importance in sacrificial rituals, highlighting its sanctity and symbolic significance.

3. Sanctuary and Sacred Ground:

Beyond individual houses, *Āyatana* also represents sacred spaces and sanctuaries. These are locations consecrated for worship and devotion, serving as spiritual hubs for communities. The *Rāmāyaṇa* and *Manu-smṛti* frequently invoke this term to describe hallowed places of refuge and prayer.

4. Site or Plot of Ground:

Extending its association with space, *Āyatana* signifies the ground plot or the foundational site of a house or structure. This meaning underlines its practical relevance in architectural and urban planning contexts within ancient India.

5. Barn or Storage Space:

In agricultural discourse, *Āyatana* refers to barns or storage areas for grain and other produce, as noted in texts like *Yājñavalkya Smṛti*. This usage reflects its importance in sustaining livelihoods and securing resources.

6. Cause of Disease:

In the realm of ancient medicine, particularly in the *Suśruta Saṃhitā*, *Āyatana* intriguingly describes the root causes of diseases. This application underscores the term's adaptability across diverse disciplines.

7. Inner and Outer Seats (Buddhist Perspective):

Within Buddhist philosophy, *Āyatana* takes on a profound metaphysical dimension. It is used to describe the six inner seats—five senses and the mind (*manas*)—and their corresponding outer objects. These twelve *Āyatanas* are integral to understanding perception and interaction with the external world.

8. Departments or Fields:

Occasionally, *Āyatana* symbolizes a domain or field of expertise, particularly in artistic or scholarly pursuits. This metaphorical use is more prevalent in Pali literature and extends the concept into realms of intellectual engagement.

Etymological Insights:

The derivation of *Āyatana* from the root "ā-yat" emphasizes extension or expansiveness. Its connotations often embody the idea of a foundation or a focal point, whether physical, spiritual, or conceptual.

Ayana: The Sanskrit term *Ayana* and its variations (*Ayāna*, *Āyana*, and *Āyāna*)

Primary Meanings and Contextual Usage

1. Motion and Path

At its simplest, *Ayana* refers to movement or motion—"going," "moving," or "walking." It is often used to denote a road, path, or way, symbolizing both physical and metaphysical journeys. For instance:

- The term *samudrāyana* is employed to describe rivers moving toward the ocean, emphasizing the flow of motion toward a goal.
- In scriptures like the *R̥gveda* and *Bhagavad Gītā*, it refers to both literal and figurative paths, such as the routes taken by warriors in formation (*ayaneṣu*).

2. Abode and Refuge

Ayana also signifies a place of dwelling or a site of resort, as seen in the *Manu Smṛti* and other texts. It connotes stability, safety, and the ultimate destination—spiritually or physically. In the derivation of the term *Nārāyaṇa*, for instance, it is explained as the abode (*ayana*) of waters (*nārā*), emphasizing a divine refuge.

3. Seasonal and Astronomical Significance

The word plays a critical role in Vedic cosmology:

- It refers to the sun's semiannual movements, divided into the *Uttarāyana* (northern solstice) and *Dakṣiṇāyana* (southern solstice). These periods symbolize transitions, associated with specific religious rituals and cosmic energies.
- It also signifies the equinoctial and solstitial points, reflecting ancient astronomical knowledge.

4. Sacrificial and Ritual Contexts

Ayana appears in Vedic rituals, denoting the "course" or "circulation" associated with

periodical sacrifices such as *Gavāmayanam*. These rites are intricately linked to the sun's journey across the celestial sphere and the alignment of time.

5. **Disposition and Nature**

As *Ayāna* or *Āyāna*, the term shifts focus to describe natural temperament or disposition, referring to the inherent qualities or tendencies of a person or entity. This usage highlights the term's adaptability to psychological and philosophical contexts.

6. **Entry and Access**

In the context of warfare or strategic arrangements, *Ayana* refers to an entry or access point in formations (*vyūha*), such as gaps in an array of troops. This emphasizes its practical application in ancient strategies.

7. **Scriptural and Philosophical References**

In certain contexts, *Ayana* signifies a scripture, treatise, or inspired writing (*śāstra*). The term also represents a way, method, or manner, underscoring its role in conveying structured paths of thought or practice. It is sometimes used to imply the ultimate spiritual goal or emancipation, as seen in the phrase from the *Śvetāśvatara Upaniṣad*: "There is no other path (*ayana*) to liberation."

8. **Arrival and Approach**

The derivative *Āyana* or *Āyāna* emphasizes "coming" or "arrival," often appearing in Vedic hymns and classical epics like the *Mahābhārata*. This meaning complements its association with movement and transitions.

9. **Ornamentation**

In the *Harṣacarita*, *Āyāna* is used to denote a particular ornament for horses, demonstrating its nuanced application in material culture.

10. **Halt or Stopping**

In contrast, the term *Ayāna* also implies "not moving," "stopping," or "halting." This usage, combined with its sense of disposition, reflects the duality inherent in its semantic range—motion and stillness.

Etymological Insights

The root *iṇa* or *yā*, meaning "to go," forms the basis of *Ayana*, with the suffix *lyuṭ* adding layers of abstract and concrete connotations. Variations like *Ayāna* and *Āyana* emerge by adding prefixes such as "a" (negation) or "ā" (intensification).

Cultural and Philosophical Dimensions

From describing the physical journey of the sun to symbolizing paths of spiritual growth, *Ayana* serves as a versatile concept in Sanskrit literature. Its integration into rituals, astronomy, and philosophical doctrines highlights its foundational role in shaping ancient Indian thought systems.

In essence, *Ayana* is not merely a word but a bridge connecting movement, stability, and ultimate transcendence, resonating across disciplines from Vedic rituals to personal introspection.

Siddha: The term Siddha has various meanings and usages across Sanskrit and Pali literature, often emphasizing accomplishment, perfection, supernatural powers, or divine status. Below is a consolidated overview:

Sidha General Meanings (Sanskrit and Pali):

1. Accomplished, Perfected, or Completed:

- Refers to something that is fulfilled, achieved, or successfully completed.
- Includes tasks, penance, or objectives.

2. Supernatural Powers or Divine Status:

- Describes beings endowed with extraordinary abilities or magic.
- Denotes semi-divine beings (e.g., Siddhas in mythology) who are immortal or reside in celestial realms.

3. Sacred or Sanctified:

- Something purified or made holy through penance, austerities, or spiritual practices.

4. Acquired or Gained:

- Includes material possessions, knowledge, or spiritual attainment.

5. Established or Valid:

- In logic, law, or grammar, Siddha implies something proven, substantiated, or adjudicated.

6. Ready or Prepared:

- Refers to something made ready, such as cooked food, matured items, or prepared medicines.

7. Satisfied or Content:

- Indicates a state of contentment or fulfillment.

As a Noun:

1. Semi-Divine Beings:

- Celestial beings with supernatural faculties, associated with the *Bhuvan-loka* (the middle air).
- They are immortal, celebrated, and sometimes confused with *Sādhyas* in later texts.

2. **Adept or Magician:**

- A person skilled in alchemy, magic, or mystic practices.
- Includes ascetics or yogis who have mastered supernatural abilities (*Siddhis*).

3. **Sage or Seer:**

- Inspired writers, sages, or prophets like Vyāsa or Kapila.

4. **Judicial Context:**

- Refers to a lawsuit or judicial trial.

5. **Plants and Substances:**

- A type of medicinal plant or root.
- Also denotes sea salt or hard sugar.

Usage in Pali Texts:

1. **Accomplished or Fulfilled:**

- Derived from *sijjhati* (to succeed), *Siddha* refers to successful accomplishment or an adept.

2. **Magician or Semi-Divine Beings:**

- Used similarly to denote beings with mystical powers, as seen in texts like *Milindapanha*.

3. **Mythological Analogy:**

- Pali sources sometimes compare *Siddhas* to *Sādhyas*, celestial beings from Vedic mythology.

Etymological Insights:

- **Root:** Derived from *sidh* (सिद्ध), meaning "to accomplish" or "to succeed."
- **Suffix:** The past participle form *-kta* implies something completed or achieved.

Special Attributes:

1. **Eight Siddhis:**

- *Siddhas* are often associated with possessing the eight classical supernatural abilities (*Siddhis*).

2. **Beatification:**

- In religious contexts, *Siddha* can indicate a state of liberation or union with the divine.

3. **Notable in Jainism:**

- *Siddha* refers to *Jinas* or *Arhats*, representing perfected beings who have attained liberation.

Cultural and Philosophical Significance:

- Siddhas symbolize the ideal of spiritual accomplishment in Indian traditions, embodying the union of human potential and divine grace.
- Their depiction varies across Hinduism, Jainism, and Buddhism but often carries a unifying theme of transcendence and perfection.

8. The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-1148

Figure:12

Table:12

𑀓	𑀔	𑀕	𑀖	𑀓𑀔𑀕𑀖
P-189	P-60	P-127	P-376	𑀓𑀔𑀕𑀖
ṭh	s	a	dh	ṭha sadha

The Sanskrit terms **Sadha**, **Sādha** and **Sadhā** as described in the cited dictionaries are detailed below:

1. Sadha:

- **Primary Meaning:**
 - Equivalent to *saha* (सह), meaning "with," "together with," or "in the same manner."
 - Found in compound constructions, as described in *Pāṇini's grammar* (6-3, 96).
- **Special Use:**
 - **Dual form (sadha or sadhā):** In Vedic contexts, may refer to "heaven and earth" (*Naighaṇṭuka* commentary by Yāska iii, 30).

2. Sādha:

- **Primary Meaning:**
 - Refers to "performance" or "accomplishment."
 - Highlights the successful fulfillment of a task or action.
- **Etymology:**
 - Derived from the root *sādh* , which means "to achieve" or "to accomplish."
- **Vedic Usage:**
 - Commonly found in texts like the *R̥gveda*, where it signifies fulfillment, successful execution, or achieving a goal.

3. Sadhā:

- **Primary Meaning:**
 - Emphasizes actions related to "putting together," "connecting," "uniting," or "composing."
 - Also implies:
 - Repairing or restoring.
 - Laying down or placing something (e.g., an arrow on a bow for aiming or shooting).
 - Imparting, granting, or bestowing something together.
- **Grammatical Forms:**
 - In the **Middle voice**, it means "bringing together" or "uniting."
 - In the **Passive voice**, it signifies being united with, getting possessed of something, or being contained within a location.
- **Etymology:**
 - A compound of *sa* (together) and *dhā* (to place or hold), emphasizing union or composition.
- **Sādha:**
 - An adjective derived from *sah* , meaning "overcome" or "conquered."
 - Appears in contexts such as the *R̥gveda* and *Atharvaveda*.

9. The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-1161

Figure:13

Table:13

△	⋈		''	◇	△⋈ ''◇
P-189	P-68	P-147	P-127	P-376	ṭha si adha
ṭh	s+i	a	a (diacritic)	dh	

Si: The Sanskrit term "Si" encapsulates a multifaceted concept encompassing auspiciousness, tranquility, and a divine association. It signifies favorable circumstances, good fortune, and positive outcomes. Additionally, it denotes a state of composure, calmness, and peace of mind. Notably, "Si" is also an epithet used to describe the Hindu deity Shiva, further highlighting its connection to divine grace and spiritual well-being.

The Sanskrit term **Ādhā**, derived from the root **dhā** (to place or put), encapsulates a range of meanings that center around the acts of placing, depositing, applying, and creating. Its usage spans from physical actions to more abstract applications, reflecting its versatility in both practical and philosophical contexts. Below is a narrative explanation of its meanings, as drawn from classical Sanskrit dictionaries:

1. To Place, Deposit, or Lodge

Ādhā fundamentally signifies the act of placing or depositing something. This can range from physical objects to abstract qualities. For instance, in **Bhagavadgītā (5.1)**, the phrase *brahmaṇy ādhāya karmāṇi* conveys the idea of dedicating actions to the Brahman. Similarly, in **Raghuvamśa (9.4)**, *gadāḥ padam ādadhau* illustrates the lodging of a malady within a region. This usage highlights the act of setting something in a specific position, whether literal or metaphorical.

2. To Apply, Propose, or Direct

Ādhā is often employed to denote the application of effort, thought, or intent. For example, **Śakuntalā (1.1)** uses *pratipātram ādhīyatām yatnaḥ*, emphasizing the direction of effort toward a specific purpose. Similarly, in the **Bhagavadgītā (12.8)**, the phrase *mayyeva mana ādhatsva* expresses the idea of focusing the mind on a single object—here, the divine.

3. To Hold, Possess, or Assume

Ādhā also conveys the sense of holding or possessing something, be it physical or abstract. For instance, in **Kumārasambhava (7.26)**, the expression *bhūyo babhau darpaṇam ādadhānām* portrays an entity assuming or reflecting an image. Similarly, the term is used to describe the conception of a child, as in **Raghuvamśa (2.75)** with *garbham ādhatta rājñī*, indicating the queen bearing a child.

4. To Support or Uphold

In its broader sense, Ādhā signifies bearing or upholding, often in the context of maintaining something significant. For instance, **Śiśupālavadha (5.4)** describes *śeṣaḥ sadaivāhita bhūmibhāraḥ*, referring to Śeṣa's role in upholding the weight of the earth.

5. To Cause, Produce, or Excite

Ādhā also connotes the creation or excitation of specific emotions, conditions, or phenomena. This is evident in **Kumārasambhava (6.2)**, where the term is used to describe the evocation of fear or wonder, as in *bhayam ādadhānāḥ* (infusing fear). Similarly, in **Mālavikāgnimitra**, it describes the generation of surprise or amazement.

6. To Supply, Impart, or Give

Another significant application of Ādhā lies in the act of supplying or imparting something to another. For example, **Raghuvamśa (1.85)** uses *śuddhim ādadhānā*, describing the impartation of purity. This meaning aligns with its role in ceremonial or ritualistic contexts, such as supplying offerings or fulfilling obligations.

7. Ritualistic and Consecratory Usage

Ādhā assumes a specialized meaning in ritualistic contexts, particularly in the consecration of fire or other sacred objects. In **Kumārasambhava (1.57)**, the phrase *tatrāgnim ādhāya samitsamidham* describes the act of kindling a ritual fire, emphasizing its ceremonial importance.

8. To Appoint or Perform

In administrative or spiritual contexts, Ādhā also implies the act of appointing or engaging in specific duties. For example, in **Raghuvamśa (7.2)**, *tameva cādhāya vivāhasākṣye* refers to appointing someone as a witness in a marriage ceremony. Additionally, it denotes the performance of vows or practices.

Linguistic and Grammatical Considerations

In its grammatical structure, Ādhā appears in various verb forms, such as **ā-dadhāti** (Parasmaipada) and **ā-dhatte** (Ātmanepada). The causative form **dhāpayati** extends its

meaning to imply causing someone to put or place something, while the desiderative form **dhitsate** expresses a wish to perform these actions.

Symbolic and Philosophical Dimensions

The term **Ādhā** transcends its literal applications to reflect deeper philosophical and symbolic meanings, such as the instillation of values, the direction of intent, and the bearing of responsibility. Its versatility mirrors the interconnectedness of physical, mental, and spiritual dimensions in Sanskrit thought.

10-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-1160

Figure:14

Table:14

		''		
P-06	P-147	P-127	P-376	Kama Adha
kama	a	a (diacritic)	dh	

The term **Kāma** has a rich and multifaceted meaning in Sanskrit literature and tradition, encompassing physical, emotional, and spiritual dimensions. Here are the main interpretations and associations:

General Definitions:

1. **Desire/Wish:** Kāma often refers to a desire or longing for something, whether material, emotional, or spiritual. This usage appears frequently in classical Sanskrit texts.
 - Example: (**saṃtānakāmāya**)—Desiring offspring.
2. **Object of Desire:** Kāma also denotes the object of one's desire or wish.
 - Example: (**sarvān kāmān samaśnute**)—He attains all his desires.

3. **Love and Affection:** It symbolizes affection or love in a broader sense.
4. **Sensual Love:** Specifically, Kāma represents the desire for sensual or carnal pleasures, and is considered one of the four puruṣārthas (goals of life), alongside dharma (righteousness), artha (prosperity), and mokṣa (liberation).

Mythological and Symbolic Representations:

1. **Kāma as a Deity:**
 - Kāma is the Hindu god of love, similar to Cupid in Greco-Roman mythology. He is often depicted with a bow made of sugarcane and arrows of flowers, accompanied by his consort **Rati** and the season **Vasanta (spring)**.
 - Mythological Account: Kāma attempted to disrupt Lord Śiva's meditation to facilitate his union with Pārvatī. Enraged, Śiva burned Kāma with his third eye. Later, he was reborn as **Pradyumna**, the son of Kṛṣṇa.
2. **Representation of Love and Spring:** Kāma is intimately associated with spring and the blooming of nature, symbolizing rejuvenation and passion.

Other Uses and Associations:

1. **Beauty and Radiance:** In some contexts, **Kamā** refers to beauty or radiance.
2. **Semen Virile:** In a physiological sense, it can denote semen.
3. **Plants and Nature:** Kāma is also a name for a type of mango tree.
4. **Metaphysical or Cosmic Kāma:** In the Vedas, Kāma represents the primordial desire that led to creation.

Linguistic Notes:

- Derived from the root **kam** meaning "to desire" or "to wish."
- Grammatical forms vary: masculine (deity or concept), feminine (**Kamā**, radiance), and neuter (object of desire).

Cultural Significance:

- **In Dharma:** Kāma is acknowledged as a legitimate goal of human life, as long as it is pursued ethically and harmoniously with **Dharma** and **Artha**.
- **In Literature:** Kāma's stories and symbolism feature prominently in classical Sanskrit poetry, drama, and epics like the Mahābhārata and Rāmāyaṇa.

11-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-1162

Figure:15

Table:15

𑀓 (P-06)	
kama	
𑀓 (P-107)	𑀓 (P-13)
k	m

12-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-281

Figure:16

Table:16

𑀓	𑀓	𑀓	𑀓	𑀓	𑀓𑀓𑀓𑀓𑀓
P-311	P-198	P-276	P-168	P-351	Pā phajja chida
pā	ph	jja	chi	dā	

The term **Pha** and its derivative **Phā** hold a variety of meanings and applications in Sanskrit, reflecting its rich linguistic and symbolic heritage.

Pha:

Meanings and Associations:

1. **Manifest/Obvious:** It denotes something that is evident or apparent.
2. **High Wind/Gale:** Pha signifies a strong wind or storm.
3. **Swelling/Expansion:** It conveys the idea of growth, enlargement, or expansion.
4. **Fruitfulness/Fertility:** Associated with productivity and abundance.
5. **Gain:** Pha symbolizes profit or benefit.
6. **Performance of Mystical Rites:** Specifically, rites to propitiate Kubera's attendants, known as **yakṣa-sādhana**.
7. **Yawning with an Open Mouth:** Refers to wind expelled while yawning.
8. **Flowing/Bubbling/Boiling:** It describes the sound or action of bubbles or boiling water bursting with a soft noise.
9. **Idle or Angry Speech:** Can represent unprofitable or heated words.

Phā:

Meanings and Associations:

1. **Heat:** Often interpreted as physical warmth or metaphorical heat, such as passion or agitation.
2. **Idle Talk:** Represents useless or unproductive speech.
3. **Increase or Increaser:** Indicates growth or something that augments.
4. **Distress/Anxiety:** Phā can signify emotional strain or trouble.
5. **Blowing or Puffing Up:** Associated with air or gas being expelled or swelling actions.

Grammatical Notes:

1. **Gender Variations:**
 - **Phaḥ:** Masculine.
 - **Phā:** Feminine or neuter depending on context.
 - **Pham:** Neuter, often referring to idle or angry speech.
2. **Etymological Roots:**
 - Derived from **phal** (to bear fruit) or **sphāy** (to swell).

Symbolic and Contextual Uses:

1. **Elemental Symbolism:** As wind or expansion, it connects to dynamic natural forces.
2. **Ritual Context:** Mystical rites associated with **Kubera's yakṣas** suggest its role in spiritual practices.
3. **Human Expression:** Describes physiological actions like yawning or emotional expressions like angry speech.

The term **Ja** and its derivative **Jā** encompass a broad range of meanings in Sanskrit, often depending on the context in which they are used. Here's a breakdown:

Ja:

Meanings and Associations:

1. General Meanings:

- **Born from/Descended from:** Often used as a suffix in compounds to indicate origin or lineage (e.g., *jalaja* – born in water).
- **Produced in or caused by:** Reflects derivation or causation.
- **Prepared from/Made of:** Indicates material or source.
- **Belonging to/Connected with:** Shows association or connection.

2. Specific Uses:

- **Speed/Swiftness:** Indicates rapidity or agility.
- **Victorious/Conquering:** Suggests triumph or success.
- **Eaten:** Reflects consumption or being consumed.
- **Birth or Production:** Refers to the act of being born or creation.
- **A Father or Parent:** Sometimes denotes a progenitor.
- **Poison:** Symbolizes harmful substances.
- **Enjoyment:** Refers to pleasure or delight.
- **Lustre or Light:** Signifies brightness or radiance.
- **A Goblin or Imp (Piśāca):** Refers to supernatural beings in Indian mythology.
- **Śiva and Viṣṇu:** Names of deities in Hinduism.

3. In Prosody:

- One of the eight syllabic meters (*gaṇas*) in Sanskrit prosody.

Jā:

Meanings and Associations:

1. **A Mother:** Often denotes maternal lineage or connection.
2. **A Husband's Brother's Wife:** Indicates a familial relation.
3. **A Race or Tribe:** Reflects a group or community of origin.
4. **Offspring:** Refers to progeny or descendants (used in plural to indicate lineage).

Grammatical Notes:

1. Gender Variations:

- **Jaḥ:** Masculine.
- **Jā:** Feminine.
- **Jaṃ:** Neuter.

2. Etymological Roots:

- Derived from **jan:** To be born or to generate.
- Related to **ji:** To conquer or triumph.

Symbolic and Contextual Uses:

1. Suffix in Compounds:

- **Aṇḍaja:** Born from an egg.
- **Jalaja:** Born in water (e.g., lotus).
- **Kulaja:** Born in a noble family.

2. Deity Names:

- **Śiva:** Associated with Ja as a name.
- **Viṣṇu:** Similarly connected to Ja in hymns and texts.

3. Symbolism:

- As light or lustre, it connects to divine or spiritual illumination.
- As swiftness, it symbolizes dynamic energy or movement.

[Source:](#) DDSA: The Molesworth Marathi and English Dictionary

phajjā (फज्जा) [or फज्या, phajyā].—m also phajjā śivaṇēm See bhōgyā & bhōmyā śivaṇēm.

The Sanskrit root "ci" is a versatile verb with multiple meanings, primarily related to collecting, gathering, and arranging.

Here are the primary meanings of "ci":

1. To collect, gather, accumulate:

- This is the most common meaning of "ci." It involves bringing things together, either physically or metaphorically.
- Examples of usage:
 - Collecting flowers from a tree: (vṛkṣaṃ puṣpāṇi cinvatī)
 - Gathering wealth or knowledge (cicīṣatām canmavatāmaladhvīm bhūtim)

2. To search, look out for:

- This meaning involves seeking something, whether physically or mentally.
- Example: Bhartṛhari 3.46

3. To pile or heap up, place in a line:

- This meaning suggests arranging things in a specific order or pattern.
- Example: (parvatāniva te bhūmā- vacaiṣurvānarottamān

4. To set, inlay, cover or fill with:

- This meaning involves placing one thing on or within another.
- Example: The passive form of "ci" (cīyate) can mean "to bear fruit, grow, increase, thrive, prosper."

In addition to these primary meanings, "ci" can also mean:

- **To observe, see, perceive:** This is a Vedic usage of the root.
- **To detest, hate:** This is another Vedic usage.
- **To fear, dread:** This is a less common meaning.

The various forms of "ci" and its derivatives can convey a wide range of nuances, making it a flexible and powerful tool in the Sanskrit language.

1. Da

As a root or in composition:

- **Meaning:**
 - Giving, granting, producing, cutting off, destroying, removing.
 - Common in compound words like (dhanada - giver of wealth) or (toyada - giver of water, i.e., cloud).

As a noun:

- **daḥ:**
 1. A gift or donation.
 2. A mountain.
- **dam:**

1. A wife.
- **dā:**
 1. Heat.
 2. Repentance.

As a verb (4th conjugation):

- **Root:** dāmyati (to tame or restrain).
 - Meanings:
 1. To be tamed or subdued.
 2. To pacify or calm.
 - Causative: **damayati** (to cause subjugation or restraint).

2. Dā

As a root:

- **Primary meanings:**
 1. To give, present, or grant.
 2. To deliver, surrender, or offer.
 3. To pay, perform, or pronounce.

As a noun:

- **dā:** Protection, cleansing, or purifying.

Conjugations & Derived Forms:

- **dadāti / dattam:** Gives / Given.
- **Desiderative:** ditsati (desires to give).

In compounds:

- Used as an ending to signify a giver or bestower, e.g., (sahasradā - giver of a thousand gifts).
- Verbal prefixes modify meanings significantly:
 - **Ā-dā:** To take or accept.
 - **Vi-dā:** To divide.
 - **Pra-dā:** To grant or surrender.
 - **Sam-dā:** To bestow or deliver.
 - **Causative forms:** Indicate causing or facilitating the root action (e.g., dāpayati = causes to give).

- In compounds, the meanings are often contextual. For instance:
 - **Agni-dā**: One who quenches or gives fire.
 - **Jīva-dā**: One who gives life.

The Sanskrit term **Chidā** and its derivations from the root **Chid** have the following meanings and contextual uses:

Meaning:

1. Primary Meaning:

- Cutting, dividing, or severing.

2. Grammatical Classification:

- **Chidā**: Feminine noun form, indicating the act or process of cutting or dividing.
- Derived from the root **Chid**, which means "to cut, split, or pierce."

Sources:

- **Chidā** is described as "cutting" or "dividing."
 - **Chidā** is mentioned as "cutting off," derived from **Chid** and found in texts like Hemacandra's Yoga-śāstra.

Usage:

- Often used in philosophical, ritualistic, or practical contexts to denote separation or division.
- May appear in compound words to signify the act of cutting, e.g., **Mātrka-chidā**, meaning "cutting off [something related to] the Mother principle."

Etymology:

- **Root: Chid** – To cut, pierce, divide.
- **Suffixes:** Added to indicate action/state or make it feminine (-ā for bhāva or abstract form).

13-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-284 and M-1155

Figure:17

Figure:18

Table:17

P-311	P-319	P-196	P-127	P-150	P-302	Pāla jha ṇa ba
pā	l	jh	a	ṇ	b,	

Masculine Form (jhaṇ)

1. Vrihaspati – The Preceptor of the Gods:

In Hindu mythology, "Jha" serves as a name for **Vrihaspati**, the divine teacher of the Devas (gods). Known as the lord of wisdom and eloquence, Vrihaspati is revered for his intellectual prowess and his role as a guiding force for the celestial beings.

2. Chief of the Daityas (Demons):

"Jha" is also associated with a significant figure among the **Daityas**, the demon clan in Indian mythology. This dual attribution to both divine wisdom (Vrihaspati) and demonic leadership underscores the term's versatile and contrasting applications.

3. High Wind:

"Jha" denotes strong winds, representing the chaotic and dynamic movement of air that can uproot or unsettle, much like the jangling sounds it also represents.

4. A Stray or Mislaid Object:

In a more literal sense, "Jha" can signify a lost or misplaced object, hinting at the themes of impermanence or the transient nature of material possessions.

5. Playing a Tune or Beating Time:

The term is used metaphorically to describe rhythmic activities, such as playing music or marking time with beats, showcasing its connection to harmony and rhythm.

Feminine Form (jhā)

1. A Cascade or Waterfall:

In its feminine form, "Jhā" beautifully symbolizes the descent of water from a height, forming a cascade or waterfall. This imagery brings to mind the graceful and relentless flow of water, its musical splashes harmonizing with nature's rhythm. The cascading water reflects both power and serenity, embodying the natural cycle of rise and fall.

Ṇa: The term 'Ṇa' in Sanskrit holds a variety of meanings and applications, ranging from philosophical concepts and mythical associations to physical structures and abstract ideas.

Primary Meanings of "Ṇa"

1. Knowledge:

"Ṇa" represents the concept of **knowledge**—the intellectual pursuit of understanding and wisdom. This association places it in the domain of learning and enlightenment, suggesting an intrinsic connection to truth and awareness.

2. Certainty or Ascertainment:

It also signifies **certainty**, the act of determining or ascertaining something with clarity and conviction. This meaning reflects a sense of decisiveness and the resolution of doubts, aligning it with clarity of thought and assuredness.

3. Śiva:

In Hindu mythology, "Ṇa" is a name for **Śiva**, the great destroyer and transformer in the Hindu trinity. As Śiva represents the annihilation of ignorance and the cyclical nature of creation, this connection adds a profound spiritual dimension to the term.

4. Vindudeva:

It is also associated with **Vindudeva**, a deity in Jain tradition, demonstrating its relevance across multiple philosophical and religious traditions.

5. An Ornament:

The word describes **ornaments**, representing beauty and adornment. This usage highlights a tangible, aesthetic application of the term, tying it to the realms of art and personal embellishment.

6. A Water or Summer House:

"Ṇa" denotes a **water house** or **summer retreat**, structures built to provide solace and coolness in the heat. This meaning reflects comfort, luxury, and a connection to nature's soothing elements.

7. A Bad Man or One Without Good Qualities:

Interestingly, it also refers to an individual devoid of virtues—a **bad man** or someone lacking noble qualities. This interpretation underscores moral and ethical dimensions, contrasting with its association with knowledge and divinity.

8. A Kind of Sound – The Sound of Negation:

The term represents a specific type of sound, often associated with **negation** or denial. This could relate to the primal sound of refusal, expressing dissent or a lack of affirmation.

9. Gift or Giving:

"Na" signifies **giving** or the act of bestowing gifts, linking it to generosity and acts of the term "**Ba**" (ब) and its variations in Sanskrit offer intriguing meanings, spanning divine associations, physical objects, and abstract expressions. Below is a detailed exploration of the term and its significance.

Primary Meanings of "Ba"

1. Varuṇa:

"Ba" is associated with **Varuṇa**, the Vedic deity of water, the oceans, and cosmic law. As the god of the celestial oceans and the keeper of universal order (Ṛta), Varuṇa embodies both the vastness and depth of the physical and spiritual realms.

2. A Water Jar:

The term denotes a **water jar**, a practical and symbolic object in Indian culture. Water jars are vessels of life, purity, and sustenance, often used in rituals to signify abundance and sanctity.

3. The Ocean:

Extending its connection to water, "Ba" signifies the **ocean**, a vast and powerful entity that symbolizes depth, infinity, and the mysteries of existence. The ocean also represents the unbounded nature of consciousness in philosophical traditions.

4. The Vulva:

In a more intimate and symbolic context, "Ba" refers to the **vulva**, representing creation, fertility, and the primal source of life. This meaning highlights the generative and sacred aspects of existence.

Meaning of "Bā"

1. Adverbial Use:

The term "**Bā**" functions as an **adverb**, with meanings such as:

- **As or like:** Used to draw comparisons or express similarity.
- **Or or either:** Employed to present alternatives or choices in a statement.

14-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-280

Figure:19

Table:18

𑀧	𑀢	𑀤	𑀭	𑀢𑀢	)	𑀢	𑀧𑀢𑀤𑀭𑀢𑀢𑀢
P-311	P-211	P-72	P-127	P-61	P-162	P-09	Pā ha śa asaja
pā	h	ś	a	asaja	chha	maha	chamaha

Ha: The term "Ha" holds a significant place in classical Sanskrit literature and is a versatile word with multiple nuanced usages. It primarily functions as an **emphatic particle**, employed to intensify or emphasize the meaning of the preceding word. In this context, it can be roughly translated into English as 'verily,' 'indeed,' or 'certainly,' serving to provide a heightened sense of affirmation or stress. For example, in phrases like "*tasya ha śataṃ jāyā babhūvuḥ*" (verily, he had a hundred wives) or "*tasya ha parvatanāradau grha uṣatuḥ*" (indeed, Parvata and Nārada stayed at his house), the particle "ha" adds weight and decisiveness to the statement.

However, in other cases, particularly in **Vedic literature**, the word is often used in an **expletive** manner, devoid of any specific meaning. Here, it merely acts as a filler or stylistic device, enhancing the rhythmic flow of verses without contributing significantly to the literal sense. For instance, in passages such as "*dvayā ha prājāpatyā devāścāsurāśca*" (Verily, there were two classes of descendants of Prajāpati, the gods and the asuras), the particle subtly underscores the divine and mythological narrative.

Occasionally, *ha* also appears as a **vocative particle**, used to address someone, calling attention in a gentle yet noticeable manner. Very rarely, it emerges in expressions of **disdain** or **laughter**, giving a tone of mockery, amusement, or scorn.

Beyond its role as an emphatic particle, the term "ha" and its derivatives (particularly *-haḥ*) hold rich symbolic and conceptual meanings across Sanskrit lexicons and spiritual contexts. These meanings extend to various domains, often reflecting profound cultural, philosophical, and mythological associations. The word takes on the following interpretations:

1. **A form of Śiva:** In one of its deeper symbolic connotations, "haḥ" is associated with Lord Śiva, the ascetic and destroyer within the Hindu Trinity (Trimūrti). This connection links the syllable to spirituality, transcendence, and divine presence.
2. **Water:** The term signifies the essence of life itself—*water*—which is vital for existence and represents purity, flow, and nourishment.
3. **Sky:** As a reference to the *sky*, "ha" evokes imagery of vastness, boundlessness, and the ethereal realm, symbolizing infinity and freedom.
4. **Blood:** It is also associated with *blood*, a life-giving fluid, representing vitality, strength, and the essence of physical existence.
5. **A cipher:** In mathematical or philosophical contexts, "ha" denotes a *cipher*, the numeral zero. This interpretation highlights concepts of emptiness, potentiality, and the infinite cycle of creation and dissolution.
6. **Meditation:** The word embodies the practice of *meditation*, pointing to inner contemplation, mindfulness, and the path to self-realization or enlightenment.
7. **Auspiciousness:** In symbolic terms, "ha" conveys *auspiciousness*, embodying good fortune, positive energy, and divine blessings.
8. **Paradise:** The term extends its meaning to signify *paradise*, a place of eternal bliss, harmony, and perfection in spiritual realms.
9. **Heaven:** Closely related to paradise, "ha" is also used as a synonym for *heaven*, a celestial abode for divine beings and souls of virtuous individuals.
10. **Drying:** On a more literal level, the word signifies *drying*, capturing a physical transformation or reduction of moisture.
11. **Fear:** Symbolizing the emotional state of *fear*, "ha" reflects apprehension, vulnerability, and human anxieties.
12. **Knowledge:** It also denotes *knowledge*, aligning with the pursuit of wisdom, awareness, and intellectual enlightenment.
13. **The moon:** The term is used as a poetic or symbolic reference to the *moon*, representing beauty, coolness, and the calming influence of lunar energy.
14. **Name of Viṣṇu:** In its divine connotation, "ha" also serves as an epithet for Lord Viṣṇu, the preserver of the universe in Hindu mythology.
15. **War or battle:** The word conveys the imagery of *war* or *battle*, signifying struggle, conflict, and valor on both material and spiritual planes.
16. **A horse:** It is sometimes associated with a *horse*, a symbol of speed, power, and nobility.
17. **Pride:** The term encompasses the concept of *pride*, representing self-respect, dignity, and at times, arrogance.

18. **Horripilation:** "Ha" signifies the phenomenon of *horripilation*, or goosebumps, often evoked by awe, fear, or profound emotional experiences.
19. **A physician:** Lastly, the word is used to describe a *physician*, someone who heals and restores health, reflecting wisdom, compassion, and care.

Source: Cologne Digital Sanskrit Dictionaries: Monier-Williams Sanskrit-English Dictionary
Sāja (साज):—mfn. together with the lunar mansion Pūrva-bhadra-padā, [Varāha-mihira's Bṛhat-saṃhitā

The term "**Cha**" encompasses a range of meanings and concepts, reflecting its utility in describing physical, emotional, and symbolic states. As an **adjective**, it primarily conveys two key ideas: purity and instability, each holding distinct connotations depending on the context.

1. **Pure, clean:** In its first and most prominent sense, *cha* refers to something that is *pure* or *clean*. This purity could relate to the physical world—like clean water, an untainted surface, or even the pristine beauty of nature—or take on a metaphorical dimension, signifying moral integrity, clarity of thought, or spiritual cleanliness. In ancient literature, purity is often associated with sanctity, perfection, and divinity, making this meaning particularly significant in ritualistic and philosophical contexts.
2. **Trembling, unsteady:** On the other hand, *cha* also describes something that is *trembling* or *unsteady*. This interpretation evokes a sense of motion, instability, or uncertainty. It might refer to a physical movement, such as a leaf quivering in the wind or water rippling on the surface, or symbolize emotional states like fear, nervousness, or excitement. The duality of meaning—purity and unsteadiness—reflects the complexities of existence, where balance and flux often coexist.

When expanded with suffixes, the term **-chaḥ** and **-chā** introduces a broader set of meanings, each providing unique insights into different aspects of life and materials:

-chaḥ

1. **A part, fragment:** The suffix *-chaḥ* signifies a *part* or *fragment* of a whole. It conveys the idea of division or incompleteness, where something larger has been broken into smaller components. This meaning holds practical relevance in describing physical objects, divisions in time or space, or abstract concepts like parts of knowledge or fragments of memory.
2. **Cutting, dividing:** Closely related to its association with fragments, *-chaḥ* also conveys the act of *cutting* or *dividing*. This meaning emphasizes the process of separation, whether literal (such as slicing an object) or metaphorical (like dividing responsibilities or breaking apart a union). It reflects themes of transformation, where something whole is changed into distinct parts.

3. **Chaḥ as Soma:** A curious and poetic interpretation found in the ancient lexicon associates *chaḥ* with *Soma*, the divine and sacred drink in Vedic rituals. Soma, often depicted as a source of energy and immortality, holds great significance in Vedic symbolism. This linkage elevates the term *chaḥ* from the mundane to the divine, connecting it to spiritual sustenance and celestial power.

-chā

1. **Covering, concealing:** With the suffix *-chā*, the term signifies the act of *covering* or *concealing*. This interpretation can refer to physical coverings—like a blanket shielding someone from the cold—or metaphorical concealments, such as hiding emotions, intentions, or truths. In literature, this idea often symbolizes mystery, protection, or secrecy, where what is hidden holds as much importance as what is revealed.
2. **An infant, a child:** Another poignant meaning of *-chā* is an *infant* or *child*. Here, the term evokes imagery of innocence, tenderness, and the beginning stages of life. A child represents potential, purity, and unshaped possibilities, reflecting the fragility and beauty of new beginnings. This association adds a layer of tenderness and compassion to the term.
3. **Quick-silver:** In a more material sense, *-chā* also refers to *quick-silver* (mercury), a substance known for its fluidity, reflective quality, and unsteady nature. Quick-silver serves as an apt symbol for something that is elusive, constantly in motion, and difficult to grasp—much like life itself. Mercury's use in ancient alchemy further enriches this meaning, as it was often associated with transformation, healing, and mystical properties.

In conclusion, the word **Cha**, along with its extended forms **-chaḥ** and **-chā**, demonstrates remarkable versatility in its meanings. Whether describing the *purity* of an object, the *trembling* of motion, the *fragmentation* of a whole, or the *concealment* of truths, the term beautifully captures various facets of life and nature. Its associations with infants, quick-silver, and even the sacred Soma further deepen its significance, linking it to themes of innocence, transformation, and the divine. This diversity of meanings highlights the richness of Sanskrit vocabulary, where even a seemingly simple word can carry profound layers of interpretation and symbolism.

Mahaḥ

1. **A festival or festive occasion:**

The primary and most poetic sense of *mahaḥ* is that of a *festival* or a joyous, celebratory occasion. It symbolizes the collective happiness of a community coming together to mark a significant event. A festival, in this context, is more than just a gathering—it reflects human emotions, shared bonds, and the radiance of relationships. For instance, phrases such as "*bandhutāhṛdayakaumudīmahaḥ*" (a festival of moonlight in the hearts of friends) evoke a profound imagery of joy, intimacy, and shared moments under the serene moonlight, often seen in works like the *Mālatīmādhava*. Similarly, *Uttararāmacarita* and *Śisupālavadhā* highlight how the essence of a festival transcends

physical presence, strengthening emotional connections even over distances. The word captures not just the outward merriment but also the *inner radiance of relationships and emotions*.

2. **An offering, a sacrifice:**

In its secondary usage, *mahaḥ* refers to an *offering* or a *sacrifice*. This meaning connects the term to the Vedic ritualistic traditions, where sacrifices (yajñas) are central acts of devotion and appeasement. Offerings, whether material or spiritual, reflect an individual's dedication and willingness to give up something valuable for a higher purpose—be it for the gods, loved ones, or a greater cause.

3. **A buffalo:**

Mahah is also used to denote a *buffalo*, an animal often associated with agricultural livelihoods, strength, and labor. The buffalo's presence in this lexicon highlights its practical importance in agrarian cultures, where it symbolizes sustenance, endurance, and resilience.

4. **Light, lustre:**

In a more abstract and philosophical sense, *mahaḥ* represents *light* or *lustre*. This meaning aligns closely with *mahas*, another related word that signifies brilliance, radiance, or splendor. Here, light takes on both a literal and symbolic role, representing illumination, wisdom, and clarity—essential qualities in both material and spiritual pursuits. The term's association with light ties it to celestial and divine forces, such as the light of the sun or the glow of knowledge that dispels darkness.

Mahā

The term *mahā* serves as a significant derivative and substitute for *mahat* (great or large) in Sanskrit grammar. It primarily appears at the **beginning of compounds**—particularly **Karmadhāraya** and **Bahuvrīhi** compounds—to convey a sense of greatness, superiority, or vastness.

1. **The grammatical role of Mahā:**

In Sanskrit, *mahā* acts as a prefix that enhances or intensifies the meaning of the following word. For instance, in a **Karmadhāraya compound**, the two members of the compound remain syntactically equivalent, and *mahā* simply denotes greatness. Examples include *mahā-rāja* (a great king) or *mahā-nadi* (a great river). Similarly, in **Bahuvrīhi compounds**, where the compound as a whole qualifies something external, *mahā* adds emphasis. For example, *mahā-yajña* (one for whom the great sacrifice is performed) or *mahā-bala* (one possessing great strength).

2. **A cow:**

Interestingly, *mahā* also carries a literal meaning as a *cow*. In ancient societies, cows were revered as sacred animals, symbolizing prosperity, nourishment, and motherhood. The cow's inclusion under *mahā* reinforces its importance as both a physical resource and a spiritual symbol, often associated with fertility, abundance, and divine grace.

3. Irregular compounds and usage:

The flexibility of *mahā* in forming irregular compounds cannot be overstated. The number of compounds beginning with *mahā* is vast, extending almost infinitely. This reflects not only the productivity of the Sanskrit language but also the cultural emphasis on expressing greatness, grandeur, and largeness through compounded words. Many such compounds hold specific or peculiar significances, encapsulating profound ideas or attributes in a concise manner.

Chamā (Pali): The Earth and Its Symbolism

In the Pali tradition, *chamā* refers to the **earth** or **ground**, reflecting its foundational and steadfast nature. The earth has long been a symbol of stability, patience, and unwavering support. It is the surface on which life thrives, the silent witness to the passage of time, and the source of nourishment for all living beings. This simple yet profound concept highlights the earth's inherent qualities—resilience, forgiveness, and endurance.

Kṣama: The Virtue of Patience and Fitness

The Sanskrit word **kṣama** beautifully blends two powerful ideas—**patience** and **competence**—each holding a mirror to the values revered in ancient Indian thought. It seamlessly oscillates between moral fortitude, physical ability, and situational appropriateness, depending on the context.

1. Patient and Enduring:

The term *kṣama* first and foremost highlights **patience** and **endurance**. In literature, this quality is often attributed to the **earth**—an eternal symbol of forbearance and resilience. The *Atharva Veda* praises the earth as "**kṣamām**"—one who silently bears all burdens while remaining steadfast. This endurance does not merely indicate the absence of reaction but a conscious act of forgiveness, a choice to remain calm and stable amid trials. In poetry and epics, patience becomes a virtue of kings, sages, and righteous individuals, emphasizing emotional control and moral strength.

2. Adequate, Able, Competent:

In practical contexts, *kṣama* signifies **competence** or **ability**—the fitness to endure, perform, or achieve. It describes someone or something *capable* and *suitable* for a specific task, as seen in phrases like *gamanakṣama* (fit for travel) or *tapahkṣama* (worthy of performing penance). Whether physical, intellectual, or moral, the ability to withstand challenges or fulfill one's duties lies at the heart of this interpretation.

3. Appropriate, Suitable, Proper:

Another important facet of *kṣama* is **propriety** or **suitability**. In classical Sanskrit drama and poetry, *kṣama* is used to denote what is appropriate or fit for a given situation, such as *ātmakarmakṣamaṃ deham* (a body suitable for performing one's duty). Here, the term reflects harmony, where an action or object aligns perfectly with its purpose or context.

4. **Endurable and Bearable:**

The word also extends to what can be **borne** or **endured**—whether a physical pain, emotional grief, or an environmental hardship. It is used to describe situations or things that do not exceed the limits of one's patience or capacity.

5. **Favorable and Friendly:**

In a softer, more personal sense, *kṣama* signifies a **friendly** or **favorable** disposition. This aligns with its association with forbearance and forgiveness, qualities that promote harmony and goodwill among individuals.

6. **Worthy and Honorable:**

Lastly, *kṣama* conveys **worthiness**, whether in terms of praise, action, or behavior. For example, phrases like *stavakṣamāḥ* (worthy of praise) highlight the honorable and deserving nature of individuals or deeds.

Related Forms and Derivatives:

- *Kṣamam* (𑀓. neuter): Represents **propriety** or **fitness**, reinforcing the importance of harmony and appropriateness in one's actions. It can also mean **battle** or **war**, where one's ability and endurance are tested.
- *Kṣamaḥ* (name of Śiva): The word gains divine significance as one of the epithets of **Lord Śiva**, who embodies infinite patience, endurance, and forgiveness.

1. **An Epithet of Durgā:**

The divine association of *kṣamā* with **Durgā**, the goddess of strength and protection, highlights its elevated spiritual dimension. As Durgā, *kṣamā* embodies both power and patience, symbolizing the balance between endurance and action.

15-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-1159

Figure:20

Table:19

P-67	P-60	P-129	P-127	P-333	P-129	Asu sara vata
asu	s	r	a	vata	r	ra

The sign P-333 is a compound sign composed of two elements: P-91 (𑀓) and P-332 (𑀔𑀕), with another variation being 𑀓𑀔. The sign P-332 might represent the dual form of either P-341 (𑀔) or P-376 (𑀕). Other dual variations of similar signs include P-377 (𑀔𑀕) and P-342 (𑀔𑀕). If P-332 is considered the dual form of P-341, its general behavior does not align with the vowel combination techniques observed in the Indus script. However, interpreting P-332 as the dual form of P-376 seems consistent with the method of combining two consonantal signs within the script. Whether this is purely coincidental or indicative of confusion during the transcription from the Indus script to Sanskrit, both readings yield the same meaning: *vaā* (interpreted as *vaya* or *vayu*) or *vata* (*vayu*), referencing the Vedic deity associated with wind.

Asu:

Core Meanings

1. Breath or Life Force:

"Asu" primarily represents **breath** or **life**, symbolizing the vital essence that sustains beings. In the **R̥gveda** (15.1.1), it is associated with the spiritual and life-giving energy, emphasizing its sacred and indispensable nature.

2. Life of Departed Spirits:

Beyond physical life, "Asu" also denotes the **life of departed spirits**, suggesting a continuity of existence beyond the physical realm, aligning with spiritual and metaphysical beliefs in ancient Indian philosophy.

3. **The Five Vital Breaths (Prāṇa):**

In plural form (asavaḥ), "Asu" refers to the **five vital airs or breaths** that animate the body:

- **Prāṇa:** Upward-moving breath.
- **Apāna:** Downward-moving breath.
- **Vyāna:** Circulating breath.
- **Udāna:** Ascending breath.
- **Samāna:** Equalizing breath.

These are essential to the physiological and spiritual systems in Vedic and yogic traditions.

4. **Wisdom (Prajñā):**

In some contexts, "Asu" signifies **wisdom**, linking breath to thought and consciousness, reinforcing the interconnection between body, mind, and spirit.

5. **Affliction:**

It can also refer to **affliction** or suffering, likely arising from the absence or disturbance of the vital breaths.

6. **Time Measurement:**

- "Asu" is a unit of time, defined as the duration taken to pronounce one long syllable.
- This connects breath to the rhythm and structure of language, emphasizing its temporal dimension.

7. **Weight Measurement:**

It represents a **sixth part of a pala**, indicating its utility in ancient systems of measurement.

Etymological Insights

- Derived from the root **asa** (to be) with the suffix **u**, it encapsulates the essence of existence and vitality.

Āsu:

1. **Soma Pressing:**

The term is primarily associated with the **pressing or distilling of Soma juice** in Vedic rituals, highlighting its ritualistic and sacred connotations.

2. **Excitation or Enlivening:**

"Āsu" conveys the act of **exciting or enlivening**, reflecting an infusion of energy or vitality, a recurring theme in Vedic literature.

Āśu:

Core Meanings

- 1. Speed and Swiftness:**
"Āśu" characterizes **quickness** or **fleetness**, describing movement or action that is swift and immediate. It conveys urgency and efficiency in performance or action.
- 2. Rice Ripening in the Rainy Season:**
The term is also used to describe a specific variety of **rice that ripens during the rainy season**, linking it to the agricultural cycle and the swift fruition of crops.
- 3. As an Adverb:**
When used as an adverb, "Āśu" means **quickly** or **immediately**, reflecting its direct application in describing rapid action.

Etymological Insights

- Derived from the root **aśū** (to pervade) with the suffix **uṇ**, it denotes pervasiveness and immediacy, extending its application to speed and quickness.

Philosophical and Symbolic Dimensions

- 1. Breath and Life (Asu):**
The breath symbolizes life and consciousness, serving as a bridge between the physical and metaphysical. The five vital airs, integral to yoga and Ayurveda, represent a harmonious balance essential for health and spiritual growth.
- 2. Swiftness and Efficacy (Āśu):**
The emphasis on speed and immediacy reflects the dynamic nature of life and the need for prompt action in fulfilling duties or achieving goals.
- 3. Ritual and Sacredness (Āsu):**
The pressing of Soma in rituals highlights the importance of vitality and rejuvenation, both physically and spiritually.

Sāra as "Essence" in Mokṣopāya

The **Mokṣopāya** (also known as the **Yogavāsiṣṭha**) elaborates on the essence of existence and perception through the term "Sāra." According to this 10th-century philosophical text, Sāra represents the **core reality** underlying all phenomena. The discussion focuses on three elements:

- **The Perceiver (Draṣṭṛ):** The observer or knower.
- **The Act of Perception (Darśana):** The process through which knowledge arises.
- **The Perceived Object (Dṛśya):** That which is observed.

In this framework:

- **Sāra is Knowledge Itself:** The text explains that the state of pure knowledge is the essence of all three—perceiver, perception, and perceived. This is compared to a flower existing in space, inseparable from the space it occupies.
- **Unity through Knowledge:** Just as the wind is but movement and the ocean is but water, all phenomena are united in their essence, which is knowledge. This essence transcends material distinctions, underscoring the interconnectedness of all existence.

Meanings of Sāra in Broader Sanskrit Literature

1. **Essential or Core Nature:**
Sāra signifies the **true essence** or the most fundamental aspect of an entity. It represents that which is enduring and meaningful, distinguishing the genuine from the superficial.
2. **Excellence and Superiority:**
In various contexts, Sāra refers to the **best or most excellent** quality of something. For instance, **Trivargasāra** in the *Kumārasambhava* emphasizes the pinnacle of human virtues—Dharma (righteousness), Artha (wealth), and Kāma (desire).
3. **Strength and Vigor:**
As in **sārabalam** (strength of essence), the term also connotes **vitality and robustness**, applicable to individuals, armies, or systems.
4. **Real and Genuine:**
Sāra is used to denote **authenticity or truth**, distinguishing the real from the illusory.
5. **Soundness and Proven Worth:**
In practical applications, such as governance or warfare (*Kauṭilya's Arthasāstra*), Sāra implies something that is **thoroughly proven** and reliable.
6. **Justice and Righteousness:**
The term also conveys fairness and propriety, aligning with moral and ethical standards.

Symbolism and Metaphysical Depth

Sāra serves as a metaphor for **purity, essence, and unity** in spiritual and philosophical discourse:

- **Philosophical Symbolism:** Sāra reflects the core truth that transcends appearances, urging seekers to look beyond the transient to find what is eternal and meaningful.
- **Interconnectedness:** It highlights the unity of all things, asserting that diverse forms and experiences share a single, unifying essence—knowledge or awareness.

Vaṭa

The Banyan Tree

"Vāta" refers to the **banyan tree** (*Ficus bengalensis*), a tree revered in Indian culture for its immense size, longevity, and spiritual significance. This majestic tree is distinguished by its expansive canopy and aerial prop roots, which create an intricate network of trunks, giving it the appearance of a forest rather than a single tree.

Cultural and Religious Symbolism

The banyan tree holds a special place in Indian traditions:

1. **Symbol of Eternal Life:**

Its perpetual growth and self-propagating nature make it a symbol of immortality and resilience in Hinduism, Buddhism, and Jainism.

2. **Sacred Connection:**

- Often associated with **Lord Shiva** and **Goddess Lakshmi**, the tree is considered auspicious and is frequently worshiped.
- It is a common site for religious rituals, meditation, and community gatherings.

3. **Cosmic Metaphor:**

The banyan tree's vast network of roots and branches mirrors the interconnectedness of life and the universe. Its shade is seen as a representation of shelter, wisdom, and protection.

Practical Significance

Beyond its symbolic meaning, the banyan tree has practical uses:

- Its large canopy provides shade, making it a preferred location for rest and refuge in rural landscapes.
- The tree is also used in traditional medicine for its various healing properties.

Vāta

The Wanderer

"Vāta" translates to "**wanderer**" and is another name for **Vāyu**, the Vedic deity of wind and the cosmic breath of life. Vāyu represents the life force that pervades the universe, vital to all living beings.

Vāta as Vāyu

1. **The Vedic Deity:**

Vāyu, the god of wind, is personified as the carrier of the cosmic prāṇa (life energy). In the **R̥gveda**, he is invoked for his strength and speed, symbolizing the power of movement and vitality.

2. **The Universal Spirit:**

Vāta, as an aspect of Vāyu, embodies the **cosmic life breath**, emphasizing the

interconnectedness of all existence. It is both a physical force (wind) and a metaphysical presence (spirit).

Philosophical Significance

In **Ayurveda**, Vāta is one of the three **doṣas** (bodily humors) that govern physical and mental health:

- **Vāta** represents the qualities of air and space, associated with movement, creativity, and dynamism.
- An imbalance in Vāta is believed to cause various health issues, emphasizing the importance of harmony within this elemental force.

Sarvata:

All-Sided Perspective

Derived from the root "sarva" (meaning "all" or "entire"), "Sarvata" conveys the idea of being **all-sided** or **comprehensive**. This term emphasizes inclusivity, encompassing multiple dimensions or aspects of a situation, object, or being.

Philosophical Implications

1. **Omnipresence and Omniscience:**
The notion of "Sarvata" is often associated with a perspective that is **all-encompassing**, mirroring divine attributes such as omnipresence and omniscience.
2. **Holistic Understanding:**
The term invites individuals to adopt a **broad and unbiased viewpoint**, encouraging an approach that takes into account every angle and perspective.

Contextual Use

In Vedic and Sanskrit literature, "Sarvata" is employed to describe entities, attributes, or actions that are universal or extend across all realms. For example:

- The concept of **sarvataḥ paṇipādaḥ**, a Vedic description of the Divine, indicates a being whose hands and feet are everywhere, symbolizing infinite reach and capability.

Sarvatā

Wholeness and Totality

The feminine form, "Sarvatā," emphasizes the state of **wholeness** or **totality**, denoting the complete integration of all parts into a unified whole.

Philosophical Context

1. **Unity in Diversity:**
Sarvatā symbolizes the **oneness of existence**, where all fragmented or diverse elements come together to form a cohesive totality. This resonates with metaphysical

and spiritual ideals found in Indian philosophy, such as the non-dualistic concept of **Advaita**, which views all as one ultimate reality.

2. The Essence of Completeness:

In philosophical works like the **Nyāyamālā-vistara**, Sarvatā is discussed in terms of absolute completeness, representing the ultimate goal of knowledge and existence—the realization of total understanding.

Symbolism in Life and Nature

- **Sarvatā** reflects the interconnectedness of life, much like the threads of a tapestry that form a single image. It underscores the importance of seeing the **big picture**, where individual parts gain meaning through their relationship to the whole.

Ra: The Act of Possessing or Being

Ra denotes the state of **possessing** or **having**, often functioning as a suffix or element in compounds to express ownership or association. For example:

- A term suffixed with **Ra** implies the inherent possession of a particular quality, attribute, or trait.
- It aligns with the Sanskrit linguistic tradition where subtle affixes modify the essence or role of a root word.

This seemingly simple term encapsulates the idea of **having mastery, possession, or identification**, integral to descriptions of characteristics or relationships.

Rā : The Giver and Grantor

1. The Act of Giving:

Rā is a root associated with **granting, bestowing, or giving**. It reflects a dynamic action of offering something valuable, which could range from tangible possessions to intangible blessings or qualities.

- **Rāti** or **Rāte** represents the act of giving.
- The participle **Rāta** (bestowed or granted) further illustrates the fulfillment of the act.

2. Rā in Compounds:

When used in compound forms, **Rā** emphasizes the role of a giver or bestower. For instance:

- A compound like **Rā-°** (e.g., Rādatta: "granted by Rā") signifies someone or something associated with the act of bestowal.

3. Symbolic Value:

In classical texts, **Rā** often embodies divine or royal generosity, representing abundance, magnanimity, and blessings.

Ra: The Joy of Being

1. Delight and Rejoicing:

As a verb, **Ra** (Ātmanepada: *ramate*) signifies **pleasure, delight, and gratification**. It embodies the emotional and spiritual act of finding joy or being content.

- **Rejoicing in Privacy:** "Rahasi Ramate" from literary sources like Mālavikāgnimitra portrays the act of finding joy in solitude or intimate spaces.
- **Fondness and Pleasure:** The term extends to experiencing satisfaction or attachment, often directed toward an object, person, or situation.

2. Varied Usage Across Contexts:

- When preceded by **vi, ā, pari,** or **upa**, it transforms into a **Parasmaipada** verb, denoting variations of delight or attachment.
- In its causal form (**Rantum**), it expresses the intent or act of making oneself or others happy.

3. Emotional and Spiritual Resonance:

Beyond its literal meanings, **Ra** captures the spiritual essence of joy and detachment, a key theme in many Indian philosophical traditions.

Philosophical Depth

The roots **Ra** and **Rā** are not merely linguistic constructs; they reflect profound ideas in Indian thought:

1. **Possession as Identity:** The notion of "possessing" attributes or qualities connects with philosophical discussions about selfhood and materiality.
2. **Giving as Divine Quality:** The act of giving is often seen as divine, symbolizing selflessness, abundance, and prosperity.
3. **Joy as Fulfillment:** Joy and delight, as expressed in **Ra**, signify a state of inner fulfillment and contentment, crucial to spiritual practices and philosophies.

16-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-1151

Figure:21

Table:20

𑖀𑖩𑖫𑖪	𑖀𑖩	𑖀	𑖀𑖩𑖫𑖪𑖀
P- 73	P- 313	W- 00	Aśa apā ru
aśa	apā	Ur/ru	

[Source:](#) Pali Kanon: Pali Proper Names
Daughter of Sakka.

Āśa and Āśā: Concepts of Consumption, Hope, and Divinity

Āśa (Eater, Consumption):

The term *Āśa* reflects the idea of consumption and nourishment, often associated with elemental or divine entities that partake in the sustenance of existence itself.

1. As the Eater:

Āśa derives from the root *aś*, meaning "to eat." It denotes "one who eats," commonly appearing as the suffix in compound words.

Examples:

- *Hutāśa*: An epithet for **fire** as the consumer of offerings in the sacred fire ritual (*homa*).
- *Āśrayāśa*: A broader concept of seeking refuge or consumption metaphorically in terms of dependence.

2. Symbolic Associations:

Āśaḥ, in specific contexts like *prātarāśa* (breakfast), alludes to sustenance that fuels life. Metaphorically, it extends to consuming experiences or emotions, as hinted in literary references such as *piśitāśadoṣaḥ* (a flaw attributed to consuming flesh).

Āśā (Hope and Direction):

Āśā encompasses a multitude of connotations, bridging emotional aspirations with spatial dimensions.

1. Hope and Aspiration:

- *Āśā*, at its core, embodies the idea of **hope** or **expectation**. In poetic and philosophical texts, it is portrayed as a dual-edged force:
 - *Positive Aspiration*: The driving force behind human ambition, fueling perseverance.
 - *Illusion and Disappointment*: A deceptive river, as illustrated in Bhartrihari's works, that creates a mirage of fulfillment but often leaves one stranded.
- It is also invoked in expressions such as:
 - **Āśā Bhagna**: Broken hope or unfulfilled expectation.
 - **Nirāśa**: Complete renunciation of hope, celebrated as leading to tranquility.

2. Spatial Dimensions:

- *Āśā* represents **quarters of the compass or directions**, merging cosmic geography with emotional longing.
- Classical Sanskrit texts craft puns that play on the dual meanings of *Āśā*—both desire and direction—as in descriptions of the sun fulfilling desires (*āśāpūraikakarma*).

3. Cultural and Mythological Personifications:

- In Buddhist literature, *Āśā* emerges as one of the **four daughters of Indra**, alongside Śraddhā (Faith), Śrī (Prosperity), and Hrī (Modesty), symbolizing the integral nature of hope in both human endeavors and divine realms.
- Additionally, *Āśā* is identified as a female lay-disciple (*upāsikā*), reflecting her spiritual dimension.

Āsa: Proximity, Seat, and Vedic Context

1. Proximity and Presence:

- *Āsa* denotes a sense of **nearness or closeness**, both physical and figurative.
- In the Vedic tradition, *āsayā* signifies proximity, often in the context of one's immediate presence or a tangible closeness to the divine.

2. As a Seat or Resting Place:

- A central theme in Sanskrit literature, *Āsa* symbolizes a **seat**, often of honor or sanctity.
- This seat is metaphorical in the *Gaṇḍavyūha* narrative, where the seat of indomitable heroes (*śūrāṅām*) signifies unassailable spiritual strength.

3. Connections with the Bow:

- Occasionally, *Āsa* may denote a **bow**, as in epic and martial descriptions where warriors wield bows with divine prowess.

Mythical and Symbolic Integrations

Āśa's Elemental Roles:

From fire (*hutāśa*) to more expansive representations of destruction and consumption, *Āśa* stands as a primal force connecting physical sustenance to cosmic processes. It aligns closely with Vedic rituals, showcasing fire's dual role as a consumer and a purifier.

Āśā as the River of Desire:

This metaphor likens human aspiration to a river that carves its way through obstacles, simultaneously reflecting dynamism and delusion. While rivers nurture life, they also mislead with their illusions—mirroring the duality of hope itself.

Āsa as a Symbol of Stability:

The term anchors itself as the essence of steadiness, whether as a physical resting place or a conceptual metaphor for closeness to truth. It suggests stability amidst life's turbulence, resonating with spiritual stillness in meditative traditions.

Apara: The Multifaceted Essence of 'Another,' 'Later,' and 'West'

Unmatched Excellence

Apara often conveys the concept of being unrivaled, unparalleled, or matchless—something that stands without an equal. The absence of a higher or superior entity encapsulates this meaning. This sense is expressed through the description of creations or entities regarded as the pinnacle of excellence, as in the verse: "*The creation of the jewel among women appears to me as truly unmatched.*" In such contexts, *Apara* aligns with words like *Anuttama* (highest, unsurpassed).

Otherness and Duality

One of the more prominent uses of *Apara* is in denoting "another" or "different," either in terms of substance, perspective, or being. This is particularly evident in various philosophical and metaphorical contexts:

1. As a Substitute:

Just as worn-out garments are replaced with new ones (*Bhagavad Gītā* 2.22), *Apara* represents a state of transition or succession.

2. As a Rival or Second Entity:

Apara may refer to something that complements or rivals the first entity, as in: "*Keśava was like another Keśava, stepping forward as his equal in glory.*"

3. As Distinct or Different:

When describing differing ages or qualities, such as those present in successive epochs (*Kṛta*, *Tretā*, and *Dvāpara* yugas), *Apara* expresses both variation and continuity.

4. Inferiority and Middling Nature:

Apara also captures the notion of mediocrity or being of the "middle sort," as seen in descriptive works addressing moderation in qualities or temperament.

The Temporal Aspect

In its temporal connotations, *Apara* refers to that which is **later**, **hinder**, or **posterior**. It is frequently used in contexts like:

1. The Latter Half of Time:

Apara marks phases such as the second half of a day (*aparā sandhyā*), the latter part of a year or season (*aparā hemanta*), or the final hours of the night (*aparā rātri*).

2. Future Actions and Outcomes:

In texts like the *Bṛhadāranyaka Upaniṣad*, *Apara* refers to what remains to be done or experienced, representing the **future and its infinite possibilities**.

Spatial Dimensions and the West

When linked to spatial orientation, *Apara* signifies the **western direction**. In classical Sanskrit literature, the west embodies both physical space and metaphorical ideas of finality or culmination, as in: "*The hero ventured into the western quarters, defying all opposition from his enemies.*" Moreover, it pairs with terms describing positions, as in *aparām diśam* (the western direction).

Connections to Ownership and Property

Apara sometimes contrasts with *sva* (one's own) to denote **belonging to another** or being **alien**. This distinction frequently appears in legal and social texts addressing property, relationships, or societal roles, as in the regulation of marriage across castes or ownership disputes (*Manusmṛti* 9.85).

Paru: The Symbol of Connection and Grandeur

Paru emerges as a term steeped in both physical and symbolic significance. Its meanings bridge the tangible and intangible, allowing it to describe both the structural and the vast:

The Joint and the Knot

In its simplest form, *Paru* refers to a **joint** or a **knot**, embodying connection and cohesion. This meaning touches upon both anatomical and structural contexts, where joints form vital links in a body or knots symbolize unbreakable ties in a construct.

A Limb or Member

Expanding from its foundational sense, *Paru* also represents a **limb** or **member**, reinforcing the idea of connection but on a larger scale. In this context, the word resonates with completeness, portraying a component essential for the functionality of the whole.

The Ocean: An Unbounded Vastness

As *Paru* transitions into a metaphorical space, it comes to signify the **ocean**. This depiction connects the tangible vastness of the sea with an essence of continuity and infinity—a boundless expanse tying the horizons together.

Heaven and Paradise

From the depths of the ocean, *Paru* soars skyward, representing **heaven** or **paradise**. It transcends its terrestrial roots to evoke celestial beauty and the promise of transcendence—a realm of divine peace and perfection.

A Mountain: The Pinnacle of Strength

Finally, *Paru* becomes a **mountain**, towering and unyielding, symbolizing resilience and stability. Whether it references a literal peak or a figurative height, *Paru* imbues the idea of something enduring, majestic, and monumental.

Pāru: The Radiance of Light and Flame

If *Paru* speaks to connection and expansiveness, *Pāru* channels the dynamic and fiery qualities of existence:

The Sun: Brilliance Personified

At its core, *Pāru* represents the **sun**, the eternal source of light and life. This celestial body epitomizes radiance, vitality, and unrelenting energy, illuminating the world and sustaining it with its presence.

Fire: The Element of Transformation

Beyond the sun, *Pāru* symbolizes **fire**, capturing its duality as both a destroyer and a creator. Fire transforms, purifies, and reshapes, embodying dynamism and the perpetual cycle of birth, destruction, and rebirth.

Apa

Derived from the verbal root *pa* (to protect or maintain), with the prefix *na* (negation), *Apa* holds various shades of meaning depending on its usage as a prefix, separable preposition, or standalone element.

3. As a Separative Preposition

When used with a noun in the ablative case, it implies:

(a) **Away from:**

- *Apa lokebhyo* (away from the worlds).

(b) **Without or outside of:**

- *Apa hareḥ* (without Hari).

(c) **Except or with the exception of:**

- *Apa trigartebhyo* (excepting the Trigartas).

Āpa

Derived from *āp-ghañ*, *Āpa* has a distinct meaning as both a standalone term and as part of compounds.

1. As a Term

- One of the eight demigods (Vasus).
- Refers to *water* as a collective body or stream.
- Symbolizes the *sky* in some contexts (*Nirukta*).

2. In Compounds

At the end of compounds, *Āpa* conveys "difficult to obtain" (*durāpa*).

Ru

As a Noun

The term *Ru* functions as a noun with several layered meanings:

1. **Sound or noise:**

Encompasses a broad spectrum of auditory expressions, whether harmonious or chaotic.

2. **Fear or alarm:**

Suggests a sense of fright or anxiety, potentially linked to sudden, loud sounds.

3. **War or battle:**

- Denotes conflict or struggle, perhaps inspired by the noise and clamor associated with warfare.

4. **Cutting or dividing:**

Indicates an act of separation or slicing, suggesting metaphorical or literal severing.

17-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-1152

Figure:22

Table:21

𑀧	॥	ॐ	𑀩	𑀅	𑀓	𑀧𑀢𑀓𑀩𑀩𑀩𑀩𑀩𑀩
P-311	P-129	P-337	P-60	P-127	P-380	Pā ratta
Pā	r	tt	s	a	dhṇa	sadhaṇa

The term **Rata** is rich in meaning, encompassing ideas of devotion, delight, attachment, and engagement across a wide range of spiritual, emotional, and practical contexts. Below is a detailed exploration of the term, based on its uses in various sources:

Rata: Devotion and Delight

1. As Devotion in Spiritual Practices

In the Śaiva tradition, **Rata** signifies **being devoted** or deeply engaged in spiritual disciplines such as recitation and meditation. The **Sarvajñānottaratantra** (9th century) elaborates on this in the context of the **Śiva-vrata**—a sacred observance in which devotees:

- **Engage in japadhyāna-rata (recitation and meditation):** This denotes a continuous and heartfelt dedication to the practices of chanting sacred mantras and meditative contemplation.
- **Dwell in temples:** Living in a sacred space symbolizes complete immersion in spiritual pursuits.
- **Control the senses and maintain silence:** Such self-discipline underscores the transformative potential of devotion, culminating in the devotee becoming "equal to Śiva" after a year of observance.

Here, **Rata** encapsulates the idea of profound focus and commitment to spiritual growth, revered by both divine beings and mortals.

2. As Delight and Attachment

In the **Pali tradition**, **Rata** (as derived from the root *ram*) conveys the state of being **delighted in** or **devoted to** something. This can signify:

- **Finding joy in an activity or state of being.**
- **Being emotionally or spiritually attached.**

This meaning ties in with Buddhist practices, where devotion (to meditation or teachings) and delight (in the practice of mindfulness) are central themes. The state of being **rata** is one of immersive contentment, suggesting that one has found fulfillment in their chosen pursuit.

3. As Emotional and Practical Engagement

According to the **Practical Sanskrit-English Dictionary**, **Rata** extends to multiple shades of meaning:

- **Pleased or delighted:** Describing a state of joy or satisfaction.
- **Fondly attached to or enamored of:** Signifying emotional or affectionate connection to a person, idea, or activity.
- **Engaged in or intent on:** Highlighting active involvement in pursuits or responsibilities, such as **gobrāhmaṇahite rataḥ** ("devoted to the welfare of cows and Brahmins") from the *Manusmṛti*.

In this context, **Rata** reflects not only an emotional state but also a sense of responsibility and action.

4. As Beloved or Cherished

The term also carries the connotation of being **loved or beloved**, suggesting that **Rata** can describe both the subject who is devoted or engaged and the object of affection or attention. This duality enriches its meaning, showing that **Rata** can imply both giving and receiving love or dedication.

Philosophical and Practical Implications

1. In Spiritual Contexts

- **Rata** embodies the highest ideals of devotion, whether to a deity (e.g., Śiva) or a practice (e.g., meditation or silence).
- It underscores the transformative power of unwavering dedication, aligning the devotee with the divine.

2. In Emotional Contexts

- **Rata** signifies affection, attachment, and joy, reflecting the human desire for connection and meaning.

- It captures the interplay of pleasure and purpose in human relationships and pursuits.

3. In Practical Living

- **Rata** extends to being deeply engaged in any endeavor, highlighting the importance of focus, commitment, and love in all aspects of life.

The term **Sādhana** is a multifaceted concept in Sanskrit, encompassing diverse practices and methods aimed at achieving specific spiritual, material, or personal goals. Its meanings vary across contexts, from devotional service and spiritual discipline to magical procedures. Below is a detailed description of its interpretations based on various sources:

Sādhana: General Definition

Sādhana originates from the root **sādh**, meaning "to accomplish" or "to achieve." Broadly, it refers to the **method or discipline adopted to achieve a specific goal**, often called **sādhya** (the object of attainment). Its application spans spiritual practices, disciplined routines, and even magical rites.

1. Sādhana in Devotional Contexts

In devotional traditions, particularly within **Vaishnavism** and **Bhakti movements**, **sādhana** signifies:

- **The regulated practice of devotional service:**
 - According to the **ISKCON Press Glossary**, **sādhana** represents the **beginning phase of devotional service**, characterized by structured and regulated practices.
 - It serves as the preparatory phase where a practitioner learns and internalizes disciplines to develop a deep connection with the divine.
- **The method to achieve a spiritual goal (sādhya):**
 - As explained in texts like **Bhajana-rahasya** and **Brhad Bhagavatamrtam**, **sādhana** is the **means to cultivate spiritual realization**, ultimately leading to pure devotion (*prema*).
 - This practice involves chanting, meditation, scriptural study, and rituals aimed at developing love for God.

2. Sādhana as Spiritual Discipline

Across **Hindu** and **Buddhist** traditions, **sādhana** encompasses any disciplined effort toward achieving enlightenment or liberation. Examples include:

- **Meditative and yogic practices:** These aim to purify the mind and body, aligning the practitioner with higher spiritual realities.
- **Structured rituals and worship:** Such as mantra chanting, deity worship, and fasting, designed to cultivate devotion and self-discipline.

3. Sādhana in Esoteric and Magical Practices

In the context of **Tantric traditions**, particularly in texts like the **Kakṣapuṭa-tantra**, **sādhana** takes on an esoteric dimension:

- It refers to **magical procedures or rituals** intended to generate worldly benefits.
- These practices are categorized under **ṣaṭkarman** (six acts), including pacifying, subjugating, attracting, and destroying obstacles or enemies.
- The **Kakṣapuṭa-tantra** illustrates a variety of such sādhanas, blending spiritual and material goals through specific rites, invocations, and rituals.

4. Variations in Meaning

Depending on the tradition or context, sādhanas may also include:

- **Practical efforts in everyday life:** Efforts made to achieve material or personal goals.
- **Spiritual endeavors:** Activities undertaken to progress on the path of self-realization or divine union.
- **Magical or ritualistic applications:** Involving supernatural aims and outcomes, especially in Tantra.

Philosophical Significance

Sādhana represents the means or process, while **sādhya** signifies the ultimate goal or achievement. The relationship between these two highlights:

- The importance of disciplined effort in realizing aspirations.
- The interconnectedness of method (sādhana) and result (sādhya), where one evolves into the other through persistent practice.

The term **Paratā** derived from the root **para** meaning "supreme" or "beyond," refers to several related concepts:

1. **Highest Degree or Absoluteness:**
 - In a philosophical sense, **paratā** signifies the **highest degree or absoluteness** of something, often used to describe the supreme or ultimate state of being. This could refer to the highest form of devotion, realization, or excellence.
2. **Devotion or Intensity:**
 - In certain contexts, **paratā** also refers to being **fully devoted or intent upon** something, especially in a spiritual or religious context. For example, it can denote someone who is completely absorbed in devotion, meditation, or service, highlighting a state of deep commitment or focus.

The term appears in various classical Sanskrit works, such as the **Rājatarāṅgiṇī** and **Bhāṣāpariccheda**, where it denotes the highest quality or a state of total dedication.

18- The Inscribed Texts on Seal H-89

Figure:23

Table:22

!@!	XX	UF	l)	3)	!@!XXUF)
P-67	P-72	P-312	P-126	P- 162	Asu śa
asu	ś	upā	ṛ	chh	upāchṛa

Upacāra (उपचार): The Sixteen-Fold Ritual of Service and Worship

In the rich and sacred tapestry of Hindu religious practices, the term **Upacāra** holds significant importance. It refers to the “**sixteen types of homage and services**” rendered during the worship of deities, particularly in connection with Lord Śiva. Found in ancient texts like the *Śivapurāṇa*, *Upacāra* signifies the act of **honoring, serving, or attending** the deity through meticulously structured rituals. These acts are a symbolic offering of love, devotion, and respect to the divine, embodying both physical and spiritual surrender.

The *Śivapurāṇa* elaborates on the worship of Śiva’s **liṅga form**—a timeless representation of formless divinity—with these sixteen *Upacāras*. These services transform a simple act of worship into a sacred, intimate experience, gradually leading the devotee toward divine grace and liberation (mokṣa).

The Sixteen Types of Homage and Services

1. Āvāhana (Invocation):

The ritual begins with the **invocation** of the deity. The devotee, through heartfelt prayers and mantras, respectfully invites Lord Śiva to be present in the liṅga or the symbol of worship. It is a profound moment where the devotee connects spiritually, creating an atmosphere where Śiva’s divine energy is welcomed.

2. **Āsana (Offering the Seat):**

Once invoked, the deity is ceremonially offered a **seat** as a mark of hospitality and reverence. The seat symbolizes comfort and respect, acknowledging the divine presence in the sanctum or space of worship.

3. **Arghya (Water Offering):**

The devotee offers **water** infused with sacred elements like sandalwood, flowers, and rice. These ritual cleanses the deity and signifies purity, honoring Śiva's divine form.

4. **Pādya (Washing of the Feet):**

Following traditional hospitality practices, the devotee washes the **feet** of the deity (symbolically). This act symbolizes humility and submission, where the worshipper cleanses themselves of ego and worldly impurities through Śiva's grace.

5. **Ācamana (Water for Rinsing the Mouth):**

A small offering of sacred water is presented for the deity to **rinse the mouth**. This mystical rite purifies the connection between the worshipper and the worshipped, signifying spiritual cleansing.

6. **Abhyaṅgasnāna (Oil Bath):**

The deity is ceremonially bathed using fragrant **oils** and sacred water. This act symbolizes rejuvenation and purification, presenting Śiva in his most exalted form—pure, luminous, and divine.

7. **Vastra (Offering of Cloth):**

Fresh **clothing** is offered to adorn the deity. The garments symbolize honor, protection, and the adornment of Śiva's infinite beauty, reflecting divine dignity.

8. **Gandha (Scents):**

Fragrant substances like sandalwood paste (chandana) or other perfumes are applied to the liṅga. This offering represents purity and devotion, filling the space with a divine aroma that signifies spiritual presence.

9. **Puṣpa (Flowers):**

Fresh, fragrant **flowers** are offered to the deity. Flowers symbolize devotion, beauty, and the fleeting nature of material existence. Each flower becomes a gesture of love and surrender.

10. **Dhūpa (Incense):**

Incense sticks are lit and waved before Śiva, spreading aromatic smoke. The upward-moving smoke symbolizes the ascent of prayers to the divine and the dissolution of ego and negativity.

11. **Dīpa (Lamps):**

A lit **lamp** is presented to Śiva, symbolizing light and knowledge. This offering dispels darkness, both physical and metaphorical, and invites divine wisdom into the devotee's life.

12. **Nivedana (Food Offering):**

The devotee offers **sacred food** or prasad to the deity. This offering reflects gratitude for the sustenance provided by Śiva and symbolizes sharing the fruits of worldly life with the divine.

13. **Nīrājana (Waving of Lights):**

Lights (usually in the form of lamps) are waved ceremonially in circular motions before the deity. This act, known as *ārati*, represents the radiance and omnipresence of Śiva's divine energy.

14. **Tāmbūla (Betel Leaves):**

A traditional offering of **betel leaves**, often accompanied by areca nuts, is presented to the deity as a mark of respect and devotion. It is a gesture of completion in traditional Indian worship.

15. **Namaskāra (Obeisance):**

The devotee offers **prostrations** and prayers with folded hands (añjali mudra) in complete surrender. This act of obeisance symbolizes humility, devotion, and the merging of the individual self with the divine.

16. **Visarjana (Mystical Discharge and Conclusion):**

The worship concludes with a formal **discharge** of the deity, where the devotee respectfully bids farewell to Śiva, thanking him for his presence and blessings. This act completes the ritual, symbolizing closure and gratitude.

Broader Interpretations of Upacāra

Beyond its ritualistic definition, *Upacāra* holds a variety of meanings in Sanskrit literature and cultural practices:

1. **Service or Attendance:** The word signifies acts of **service**, whether to a deity, a person, or an ideal. In a broader sense, it includes nursing the sick, caring for elders, or attending to responsibilities with dedication.
2. **Medical Treatment (Physicking):** In contexts relating to medicine, *Upacāra* refers to the **practice of healing** and administering care. It reflects compassion, expertise, and the desire to relieve suffering.
3. **Practice and Profession:** *Upacāra* also denotes one's **profession** or the practice of a particular skill or art. It highlights discipline, consistency, and mastery.
4. **Offering or Gift:** In some contexts, *Upacāra* implies presenting **gifts, delicacies, or bribes**—a gesture reflecting an exchange of goodwill, respect, or persuasion.

5. **Elliptical Speech:** Linguistically, *Upacāra* refers to a **form of speech** that uses ellipsis or inference. Here, the word captures the subtle art of communication, where deeper meanings are implied rather than explicitly stated.

19- The Inscribed Texts on Seal H-93

Figure:24

Table:23

𑀘	𑀅	𑀘𑀅
P-187	P- 296	ḍhi pa
ḍhi	p	

Dhi: The Essence of Thought, Imagination, and Devotion

The term **Dhi** emerges from the rich linguistic and philosophical depth of Sanskrit, embodying ideas that traverse thought, knowledge, and spiritual devotion. It serves as a profound representation of the human mind's intellectual and emotional faculties.

1. A Thought, Intention, or Purpose

At its core, *Dhi* encapsulates the **thoughts and intentions** that guide human action. It signifies not just idle ideas but deliberate purposes, reflective of an individual's inner desires and motivations. In poetic works like the *Kirātārjunīya*, *Dhi* serves to articulate the contrast between one's own intentions and another's will, as seen in the line: (*imām ahaṃ veda na tāvakīṃ dhiyam*), meaning "I understand my own intention, but not yours." Here, *Dhi* symbolizes the unspoken thought process, a subtle distinction of one's mental world.

2. Imagination, Fancy, and Conception

Dhi extends beyond mere reasoning to encompass **imagination** and **fancy**, reflecting

the boundless creativity of the human mind. It refers to the power of conception—an ability to visualize what does not yet exist or comprehend abstract ideas. In Kālidāsa's *Kumārasambhava*, the poet declares: (*na dhiyāṃ pathi vartase*), which translates to “*You do not walk the path of imagination.*”

This phrase elevates *Dhi* to the realm of poetic creativity and vision, showcasing how the mind can transcend the ordinary.

3. Devotion and Prayer

Moving into the spiritual dimension, *Dhi* takes on the profound meaning of **devotion** and **prayer**. It symbolizes the focused concentration of the mind during worship or meditation, where all thoughts converge toward the divine. In this sense, *Dhi* becomes the pathway through which spiritual seekers experience communion with higher realities.

4. Knowledge and Science

In philosophical and scholastic contexts, *Dhi* represents **knowledge** and **science**, signifying wisdom that arises from deep contemplation and understanding. It is not mere information but the insight gained through reflection and reasoning, essential for guiding one's life.

5. Sacrifice

Another less common yet profound interpretation of *Dhi* is as an act of **sacrifice**—a selfless offering made with intent and thoughtfulness. This reflects the connection between thought (mental sacrifice) and action, aligning oneself with divine or higher principles.

The root "Ḍhi" appears to be a more appropriate choice than "adhi," as "Ḍhi" is often identified as the initial root in the Indus texts. In Sanskrit, "dhi" seems to serve as a later, softer phonetic variation of the same term. Additionally, the combination of "Ḍhi" with "pa" aligns well with the linguistic structure observed in the Indus texts.

Adhipa: The Sovereign Lord and Protector

The word **Adhipa** beautifully encapsulates the idea of rulership, authority, and lordship, embodying the essence of a **leader** or a **sovereign protector**. Derived from *adhi* (over) and *pa* (protector, ruler), it refers to one who presides over others with responsibility, authority, and care.

1. Lord, Ruler, and King

At its simplest, *Adhipa* denotes a **king** or **sovereign ruler**—the one entrusted with the well-being and governance of his people. In royal contexts, this title evokes power tempered with duty, as seen in the verse from the *Raghuvamśa*: (*atha prajānām adhipaḥ prabhāte*), meaning “*At dawn, the ruler of the people arose.*” Here, *Adhipa* highlights the king's role as the guardian of his subjects, reflecting an ideal leader who wakes at the first light to serve his kingdom.

2. Symbol of Authority in Compounds

Adhipa is most commonly found as a compound, emphasizing the authority over a particular domain:

- **Narādhipa:** Lord of men; a king or emperor.
- **Gajādhīpa:** The lordly elephant, symbolizing grandeur, strength, and leadership in the animal kingdom.
- **Nāgādhipa:** The lord of serpents, often referring to mythical or celestial beings in Hindu and Buddhist traditions.

3. A Guardian and Protector

Beyond mere rulership, *Adhipa* implies **protection** and guardianship. A true *Adhipa* is one who shields his people, territory, or domain from harm, ensuring safety and prosperity. This idea transcends into spiritual domains where divinities are addressed as *Adhipas*, highlighting their cosmic role as protectors of dharma (righteousness) and devotees.

4. A Figure of Responsibility

Embedded within *Adhipa* is the responsibility of leadership. It is not just about wielding power but about governing with wisdom, fairness, and compassion. A ruler (*Adhipa*) is seen as a servant of his people, echoing the philosophy that true leadership lies in selfless service.

The terms **Dhi** and **Adhipa** together capture the nuances of human thought, imagination, and leadership. *Dhi* reflects the journey of the mind—from fleeting ideas to profound knowledge and spiritual devotion—while *Adhipa* personifies the qualities of a ruler and protector, responsible for the well-being of his people and domain. Whether seen as individual concepts or within broader contexts, these words represent ideals that transcend time, emphasizing the unity of thought, action, and duty in both personal and societal spheres.

20-The Inscribed Texts on Seal L-161

Figure:25

Table:24

𑀧𑀺	(𑀭𑀭𑀭)	𑀭	𑀮	𑀧𑀺(𑀭𑀭𑀭)𑀭𑀮
P- 311	P- 140	P- 127	P- 311	Pā gri ta
Pā	gri	a	t	

Giri: The Revered Mountain and Symbol of Immovable Strength

The word **Giri**, rooted in the ancient Sanskrit lexicon, carries profound meanings that span the physical, symbolic, and spiritual realms. It is a term that resonates with grandeur, steadfastness, and venerability, often connected to mountains, rocks, and those who are held in high esteem.

1. The Mountain: A Symbol of Stability and Strength

At its most fundamental level, *Giri* signifies a **hill, mountain, or elevation**—a massive structure that rises steadfastly from the earth toward the heavens. Mountains have always been revered in Indian thought as embodiments of **strength, immovability, and timeless endurance**.

- In poetic traditions, *Giri* is invoked to convey steadfastness and fortitude, as reflected in the lines: (*nanu pravāte'pi niṣkampā girayah*), meaning “*Even amidst fierce winds, the mountains remain unmoved.*” Here, the mountain (*Giri*) becomes a metaphor for **resilience** in the face of adversity, a reminder of the unshakable resolve required to endure life’s challenges.
- Similarly, mountains are often depicted as the guardians of landscapes, rising like natural fortresses that inspire awe and reverence. In a philosophical sense, they signify **ascension**—a journey from the earthly to the divine.

2. A Huge Rock: The Unyielding Presence

Beyond mountains, *Giri* also refers to a **massive rock**—solid, unyielding, and formidable. These rocks symbolize stability and permanence, offering a tangible representation of strength that stands the test of time. In both literal and figurative senses, rocks are foundations upon which the earth’s grandeur rests, much like *Giri* serves as a foundation of faith, respect, and steadfastness.

3. A Disease of the Eyes: A Rare Usage

In a less common context, *Giri* intriguingly refers to a **disease of the eyes**. This association, though rare, highlights an underlying paradox—while the mountain represents clarity and strength, its connection to an eye ailment reflects an impairment in **vision**. Perhaps it serves as a reminder that even strength can be obstructed by limitations, whether physical or metaphorical.

4. The Venerable and Worshipful

Derived from its association with elevation and grandeur, *Giri* also functions as an **adjective** meaning **venerable, respectable, or worshipful**. Much like mountains command reverence for their immensity and endurance, individuals who embody wisdom, patience, and fortitude are equally deserving of respect.

5. An Honorific Title for Saṃnyāsins

In spiritual traditions, particularly among renunciates, *Giri* is used as an **honorific title** for **Saṃnyāsins** (ascetics or monks) who have relinquished worldly attachments to pursue a life of spiritual enlightenment. It is often seen as part of their name, symbolizing their association with steadiness, endurance, and higher spiritual knowledge. Examples include names like **Ānandagiri** (*Ānanda* meaning bliss, *Giri* representing steadfastness), where the title reflects the aspirant’s spiritual journey toward unwavering bliss and liberation.

The mountain imagery here aligns perfectly with the qualities expected of renunciates—they are steadfast like a mountain, unmoved by worldly storms, and grounded in their pursuit of truth.

The term **Giri** beautifully encapsulates the awe-inspiring qualities of mountains while extending into symbolic and spiritual meanings. Whether describing the immovable grandeur of a **mountain**, the enduring solidity of a **rock**, or the revered status of **spiritual leaders**, *Giri* reflects qualities of strength, endurance, and respect. It serves as a timeless reminder of the power of resilience and stability—an unwavering force in a constantly changing world.

21-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-1156

M-1156 a

Figure:26

Table:25

𑀧	𑀭	𑀢	𑀓	𑀠	𑀧𑀭𑀢𑀓𑀠
P-311	P-260	P-204	P-83	P-68	Pā hri ā śam si
Pā	hri	aa	śam	si	

Hari

As an Adjective

1. Color References:

- Green or greenish-yellow (*Bhāgavata* 1.2.11).
- Tawny, bay, or reddish-brown (*Raghuvamśa* 12.84).
- Yellow (*Mahābhārata* 6.65.52).

As a Noun

1. Deity Names:

- **Viṣṇu**: Often associated with his preserving qualities (*Raghuvamśa* 3.49).
- **Indra**: Lord of heaven (*Raghuvamśa* 8.79).
- **Śiva**: Another prominent deity.
- **Brahman**: Symbolizing the supreme cosmic spirit.
- **Yama**: Lord of death and justice.

2. Celestial Bodies:

- The **sun** (*Bhāgavata* 12.6.73).

- The **moon** (linked to light and serenity).
3. **Nature and Beings:**
- A **ray of light**.
 - **Fire**: Symbolic of energy and transformation.
 - **Wind** (*Rāmāyaṇa* 1.32.23).
4. **Animals:**
- **Lion** (*Bālarāmāyaṇa* 1.5,51).
 - **Horse**, including Indra's celestial horse (*Mahābhārata* 3.165.1).
 - **Ape** or **monkey**, especially in connection to *Rāmāyaṇa* and the *Vānara* allies (*Uttararāmacarita* 3.45).
 - **Cuckoo, frog, parrot, snake, peacock**.
5. **Astrological and Other Entities:**
- The zodiac sign **Leo**.
 - An **organ of sense (indriya)** (*Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad* 2.5.19).
6. **Other References:**
- **The poet Bhartṛhari**.
 - **Tawny green or yellow color** as an abstract concept.

In Sanskrit literature, the syllable *Aḥ* is imbued with a wealth of symbolic and metaphorical meanings. Its interpretations extend across religious, mythological, cosmological, and philosophical domains, capturing the essence of various deities, phenomena, and concepts. Below is a detailed narrative of its multifaceted usage:

1. Names of Deities and Cosmic Entities:

The syllable *aḥ* is attributed to several significant figures in Hindu cosmology, reflecting their diverse aspects and universal significance:

- Kṛṣṇa: Representing the divine, transcendental form of Vishnu.
- Śiva: Embodying destruction and regeneration in the cosmic cycle.
- Brahmā: The creator within the Hindu trinity (*Trimūrti*).
- Indra (Śakra): King of gods and ruler of the heavens.
- Soma: The personification of the moon or the sacred elixir of immortality.
- Vāyu (Anila): The wind deity and regulator of *prāṇa* (life force).
- Agni (Anala): The fire deity central to rituals and transformation.

- Sūrya: The solar deity, embodying life and light.
- Yama: The god of death, guiding the departed souls.
- Kāla: Time personified, symbolizing inevitability and change.
- Vaiśvānara: The cosmic fire, signifying the collective life energy.
- Praṇava: The sacred syllable "Om," representing the ultimate reality (*Brahman*).

2. Symbolic Meanings in Philosophy and Ritual Contexts:

- A representation of life and joy: It is used metaphorically for a happy man (*sukhī*).
- Cosmic principles: Referring to natural cycles such as Vasanta (spring) and Kāla (time).
- Sacrifice and purity: Associated with the flame of the sacrificial fire and efficacious mantras (Siddha mantra).

3. Metaphors in Literature and Symbolism:

- Objects and phenomena: The syllable expands its usage to represent:
 - A courtyard (*antahpura*), often signifying a sacred or royal space.
 - The head of a cock, indicating sharp vision or vigilance.
 - The disc of the moon, symbolizing serenity and reflection.
 - Chariot components such as reins or wheels, emphasizing movement and control.
- Adornment and beauty: *Aḥ* denotes ornaments, symbolizing material and metaphysical embellishments.
- Specific forms:
 - A tortoise, likely indicating stability or perseverance.
 - Umā, another name for Goddess Pārvatī, emphasizing feminine grace and power.

4. Linguistic and Grammatical Associations:

- Mantras and sacred utterances: It plays a role in *praṇava* (sacred syllables) and other Vedic chants, affirming its spiritual potency.
- Greatness or significance: Often linked with grandeur and respect.

Śam:

The term *śam* serves as a versatile root in Sanskrit with a rich spectrum of meanings and applications, especially significant in both ritualistic and literary contexts. It belongs to the 4th class in the *Parasmaipada* conjugation system, with variants such as *śāmyati*, *śamati*, *śamyati*, and *śamnāti* appearing in Vedic and classical texts. The root forms also extend to specialized

usages like imperative (*śamniṣva*, *śamiṣva*), perfect tense (*śaśāma*), and aorist (*aśamat*, *aśamiṣthās*). The causative (*śamayati*, occasionally *śāmayati*) highlights actions intended to pacify or alleviate.

Key Interpretations:

1. As exertion or toil:

Śam reflects intense activity, often linked to sacred rituals (*Ṛgveda*) or the preparation of offerings (*Vājasaneyī Saṃhitā*).

2. As cessation or quietude:

It implies an end to activity or turmoil, symbolizing peace or satisfaction (*Taittirīya-saṃhitā*, *Śatapatha-brāhmaṇa*). This usage evolves into metaphoric extensions like extinguishing flames or subduing disturbances (*Mahābhārata*, *Kāvya literature*).

3. In a destructive sense:

The root also encompasses ending through conquest, destruction, or death, as seen in martial or natural phenomena (*Kāṭhaka*, *Kālidāsa*).

4. Causal Usage:

The causative forms emphasize actions of appeasement or destruction, such as pacifying a tumultuous situation or extinguishing fire (*Ṛgveda*).

Śam:

In its adverbial form, *śam* signifies auspiciousness, fortune, and well-being. Found frequently in Vedic literature, this meaning highlights positive outcomes and harmonious states. Typical usage often occurs in fixed phrases like *śam yoḥ* or *śam ca yoś ca* ("happiness and welfare"), where it pairs with auxiliary verbs like *bhū*, *as*, *kr*, or stands alone for succinct blessings.

Śi is a Sanskrit term with rich connotations that encompass both spiritual and philosophical dimensions. Its meanings reflect auspicious qualities, emotional states, and divine symbolism. Below is a detailed narrative description of its significance:

1. Auspiciousness and Good Fortune:

The term *śi* symbolizes positive attributes associated with prosperity and favorable outcomes. It conveys an overarching sense of wellbeing and success, often linked to spiritual merit or divine blessings. In this context, *śi* is used to denote states or outcomes that bring happiness and fulfillment, aligning with the principles of harmony and cosmic order.

2. Composure and Tranquility:

As a representation of composure, *śi* embodies calmness, peace, and inner serenity. It is often invoked in contexts where emotional stability or mental equilibrium is valued. In philosophical discourse, *śi* can signify the state of equanimity achieved through meditation, self-discipline, or alignment with higher principles. This tranquility reflects a harmonious connection between the individual and the cosmos.

3. An Epithet of Śiva:

The term is also associated with Lord Śiva, one of the principal deities of Hinduism. In this usage, *śi* highlights Śiva's qualities as the embodiment of auspiciousness, destruction of ignorance, and bestower of peace. Śiva's role as a cosmic regulator, bringing balance through creation and dissolution, is encapsulated in this simple yet profound epithet. It reinforces his transcendental nature, combining the forces of benevolence and transformative power.

Asama: carries multiple nuanced meanings in Sanskrit, depending on its usage:

As an Adjective:

1. Numerical Reference:

- Uneven or **odd** (as in numbers).
- Example: (*asamaśīlāḥ khalu mṛgāḥ*), meaning "animals are of unpredictable or uneven temperament." (*Bālarāmāyaṇa* 1.2).

2. Relational Reference:

- **Unequal** in space, number, or dignity, denoting disparity.
- Example: (*asamaīḥ samīyamānaḥ*), meaning "compared with those who are not equals." (*Pañcatantra* 1.74).

3. Superlative Quality:

- **Unequaled, matchless, or unsurpassed** in excellence or merit.
- Example: (*vādyaviśeṣāṇāmasamaḥ śrotā*), meaning "an unsurpassed listener of musical instruments" (*Kumārasambhava* 12).

4. Topographical Reference:

- Uneven or **not level** (e.g., rough or rugged ground).

22-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-1154

Figure:27

Table:26

◊Ψ	△	⋈	⊙	⌈	◊Ψ△⋈⊙⌈
???	P-189	P- 68	P- 354	P- 283	Vada ṭha siva u
vada	ṭh	si	va	u	

1. The Pleasing Sound: An Aesthetic Representation

In the context of the Śivapurāṇa, *Vāda* refers to the **pleasing sound** of musical instruments, particularly the **tabor** (a type of drum).

- In traditional Indian literature, sound holds deep significance as it is believed to be divine and transformative. Instruments like the tabor produce rhythmic and resonant *vāda*, enchanting listeners and creating an atmosphere of **devotion** and **celebration**.
- Such harmonious sounds are often associated with worship, festivities, and spiritual ceremonies, serving as a medium through which **divinity is invoked** and **joy is expressed**.
- The imagery of *vāda* in this sense evokes scenes of temples echoing with rhythmic drumming, where the steady beat of the tabor lifts the soul toward higher realms.

2. Vāda as Discussion: A Nyāya Perspective

Moving into the intellectual domain, *Vāda* takes on the profound meaning of “**discussion**”. This definition emerges from the Nyāya school of philosophy, specifically the teachings found in the *Nyāya-sūtras* by Akṣapāda.

- Within the system of **Nyāya**, which emphasizes logical reasoning and critical thinking, *Vāda* is one of the **sixteen categories of discussion** (*padārthas*). These categories represent a method of systematically analyzing everything that is **knowable** and **nameable** in the universe.

- Here, *Vāda* denotes a dialogue conducted with the aim of **mutual understanding** and **discovery of truth**. It is characterized by:
 - **A clear thesis** (*pratijñā*),
 - **Sound reasoning** (*hetu*), and
 - **Conclusion** (*nigamana*).
- Unlike mere argumentation, *Vāda* encourages **objectivity**, **respect for opposing viewpoints**, and the use of **valid logic** to arrive at the truth. It reflects the Indian intellectual tradition's emphasis on **constructive dialogue** over confrontational disputes.

3. Vāda as Debate: The Arena of Philosophy

In **Śaiva and Tantric traditions**, as well as in other philosophical contexts, *Vāda* refers to a **debate**—a rigorous exchange of ideas between opposing perspectives.

- As described in texts like the *Svacchandatanthroddyota* (which alludes to *Nyāyasūtra* 1.2.1), *Vāda* is a structured form of discourse that embraces both the **thesis** and the **antithesis**.
- Unlike fruitless arguments, true *vāda* is defined by the **absence of bias** (*vītarāga-kathārūpa*), meaning that participants approach the debate with an open mind, free from attachment to their positions.
- The purpose of *vāda* in such contexts is to facilitate **clarity of thought**, **refinement of ideas**, and ultimately the **attainment of knowledge**.

In the philosophical sense, *vāda* is a **battle of wits**, where reason and logic are wielded as tools to uncover truth. It embodies the spirit of intellectual humility, where victory is not measured by defeating an opponent but by **progressing toward enlightenment**.

4. The Significance of Vāda Across Realms

Whether in the form of a rhythmic sound that **delights the soul**, a thoughtful discussion that **seeks understanding**, or a structured debate that **tests reason**, *Vāda* is a celebration of expression in its purest forms:

- It is **pleasing**, like the rhythmic sound of the tabor in worship, offering joy and spiritual connection.
- It is **constructive**, like philosophical discussions in Nyāya, encouraging intellectual growth and clarity.
- It is **rigorous**, like formal debates in Śaiva philosophy, challenging the mind to transcend biases and seek higher truths.

Siva: The Safe Haven and Auspicious Bliss

The term *Siva* carries layers of meaning across linguistic and philosophical traditions, evolving into a profound symbol of **safety**, **auspiciousness**, and **divine bliss**. Whether viewed as an adjective describing security, a state of Nirvāṇa, or a reference to the deity Śiva himself, the term encapsulates the ideas of **shelter**, **happiness**, and **transcendence**.

1. Siva as Shelter and Safety: The Protective State

In the **Pali tradition**, the adjective *Siva* denotes something that is **sheltering** or **safe**—a haven that protects individuals from harm or danger.

- It symbolizes a place where the **mind and body** find respite, free from the turbulence of worldly suffering. This notion of *Siva* as a "safe place" takes on profound significance in Buddhist philosophy, where **safety** represents freedom from the cycle of **saṃsāra**—a state of **peace and liberation**.
- *Siva* is also used metaphorically to represent **Nirvāṇa**, the ultimate sanctuary where suffering ends and eternal bliss begins. This aligns perfectly with the Buddhist vision of the **unconditioned state**, a realm untouched by sorrow or impermanence.

Imagine a weary traveler on a long, arduous journey. The word *Siva* evokes the image of reaching a peaceful refuge—a **shelter of serenity** that offers relief, protection, and the promise of freedom.

2. Siva as Auspicious and Blissful: A State of Happiness

In a broader sense, *Siva* carries the meaning of "**auspicious**," "**happy**," or "**fortunate**", as seen in Vedic and early Buddhist texts.

- It describes a state of **harmony** and **blessedness**, where conditions align to create a sense of **happiness and fortune**. In its neuter form (*sivam*), it directly translates to **happiness, bliss, or fortunate existence**.
- For instance, in Buddhist verses such as the *Sutta Nipāta*, the word *Siva* is invoked to represent a **state of well-being**, a life lived in peace and contentment—a stark contrast to the chaos of suffering.

This understanding of *Siva* as a symbol of auspiciousness resonates with the broader Indian cultural ethos, where words connoting **good fortune** and **positive energy** hold immense spiritual value. It speaks of the innate human desire for happiness and the ways in which individuals seek a state of **inner peace** and **balance**.

3. Siva as the Divine: The God of Auspiciousness

In addition to its abstract meanings, *Siva* also refers to **Śiva**, the revered deity of the Hindu pantheon.

- Known as "**the Auspicious One**," Lord Śiva embodies both the transcendent and immanent aspects of existence. As a god, he represents:

- **Destruction and Renewal:** Śiva, the cosmic dancer (Natarāja), destroys in order to create, ensuring the cycle of life continues unhindered.
- **Meditation and Nirvāṇa:** Depicted in deep meditative repose, he embodies the ideal of renunciation and ultimate liberation.
- **Shelter and Protection:** Śiva is a source of refuge for devotees, offering spiritual safety and the promise of divine grace.

For followers of Śiva, his name becomes a mantra—a sound that invokes protection, auspiciousness, and the potential for liberation. To utter *Siva* is to call upon a presence that transcends the ordinary, bringing individuals closer to the eternal **state of bliss**.

U: A Multilayered Sound and Symbol

The syllable **U** holds profound significance in **Sanskrit grammar, literature, philosophy, and spiritual symbolism**. As a single letter, it resonates deeply in Vedic, classical, and mystical contexts, representing **sound, divinity, and linguistic elegance**.

1. U as a Sacred Symbol and Divine Name

- In spiritual traditions, **U** is associated with **Śiva**, forming the **second syllable** in the primordial sound **Om (A-U-M)**.
 - **Om** represents the cosmic vibration that underlies creation, existence, and dissolution.
 - Each syllable (A, U, and M) corresponds to one of the three major deities of Hinduism:
 - **A** represents Brahmā (creation),
 - **U** represents **Śiva** (destruction and transformation),
 - **M** represents Viṣṇu (preservation).
- **U** also symbolizes **Brahmā** and the **orb of the moon** in its celestial form, tying it to **time cycles** and **divine rhythm**.
- This cosmic connotation elevates **U** beyond its phonetic form, connecting it to **timelessness** and the **divine trinity** (Brahmā, Viṣṇu, Śiva).

Imagine **U** as the harmonious middle sound—a bridge connecting **creation and dissolution**—where transformation occurs, embodying the power of Śiva.

2. U in Language: A Sound of Emphasis and Emotion

In **Sanskrit literature**, **U** serves various linguistic and rhetorical purposes:

- **Interjection:**
 - As an emotional sound, **U** expresses a range of feelings:
- **Calling or summoning:** For example, when Pārvaṭī was lovingly addressed as "**Uma**" by her mother, it contained the syllable **U** (*u me iti*).
- **Anger, compassion, command, or interrogation:** The context shapes its tone and meaning.

- For instance, in Kālidāsa's *Kumārasambhava* (1.26): (*u meti mātrā tapaso niṣiddhā*)
 - Here, Pārvatī is lovingly restrained during her ascetic practices. The word "u" reflects the tender care of her mother's voice.
- **Particle of Emphasis:**
 - In Vedic usage, **U** often serves as a **restrictive or emphatic copula**, conveying meanings such as **"and," "but," "now," or "I ask"**.
 - In combination with words like **atha** (now, then) or **kim** (what), **U** enhances the intensity or focus of a statement.
 - Example: (*u-u*) or (*uta*)—meaning "on the one hand... on the other hand" or "partly... partly."

Through its linguistic versatility, **U** becomes a subtle yet powerful tool to infuse emotion, emphasis, and rhythm into language.

3. U in Sound and Nature: Roar and Noise

From a **phonetic perspective**, **U** symbolizes sound in its primal form:

- It refers to making a **noise, roaring, or bellowing**, as observed in natural phenomena.
- For example, the roar of a **bull** or the rumble of a **storm** can be captured by the resonance of **U**—deep, powerful, and vibrating.

The syllable **U** reflects the **primordial sounds** found in nature and life, which later became organized into **mantras** and **chants** in Vedic traditions.

4. U as a Metaphor: The Orb of the Moon

Symbolically, **U** is linked to the **moon**, a celestial body revered across traditions:

- The moon represents **time cycles, change, and calm radiance**, much like the syllable **U** bridges states of being.
- Just as the moon transitions through phases, **U** signifies the transition between creation (**A**) and dissolution (**M**) within the cosmic sound Om.

23-The Inscribed Texts on Seal H-90

Figure:28

Table:27

अ	क	र	थ	उ	अक रथ उ
P- 103	P- 214	P- 56	P- 89	P- 283	aṭha ka rha thoṇ u
aṭha	k	rh	thoṇ	u	

Atha: The Sanskrit term *atha* serves as a multifaceted linguistic device deeply embedded in ancient Indian texts and traditions. It functions as an auspicious particle marking the beginning of an event, discourse, or exposition. Rooted in classical Sanskrit grammar and literature, *atha* introduces not just words but also sets the tone of anticipation, reverence, and purpose.

In its primary role, *atha* assumes the responsibility of initiating **an event or thought process**. It can be perceived as an inceptive particle—a ceremonial harbinger for new beginnings. Whether it introduces a conversation, a question, or a revelation, *atha* exudes a sense of sacredness. For example, ancient texts such as the *Vedas* or *Upanishads* often commence with *atha*, signifying an auspicious and solemn start, as if invoking divine favor. This introduction forms the transition into knowledge, wisdom, or dialogue.

Beyond its ceremonial connotation, *atha* unfolds multiple layers of meanings based on its usage:

1. **Temporal Significance – "After":** *Atha* can convey a temporal transition, expressing "after" as in the sense of what follows. It serves to guide the reader or listener through a sequence, establishing a natural flow from one event or topic to another.
2. **Conjunctive Use – "And":** In a conjunctive sense, *atha* operates like the word "and," stringing together statements, clauses, or concepts. It acts as a bridge that sustains the connection between thoughts.
3. **Premising – "Now":** Perhaps one of its most characteristic applications is its inceptive usage as "now," marking the point at which something significant is to begin. Whether

used in discussions, philosophical treatises, or epic tales, *atha* signals an emphasis on the present moment, inviting attention to what is about to be stated.

4. **Interrogative Function – "What":** Curiously, *atha* can also take on an interrogative tone, subtly suggesting the question "what" when used in appropriate contexts. This adds a tone of inquiry, facilitating reflective exploration of ideas.
5. **Comprehensive – "All":** *Atha* has the capacity to stretch its meaning to imply comprehensiveness. When used so, it signifies "all," capturing an inclusive perspective. This expansive use is particularly prominent in texts aiming to offer holistic or overarching explanations.
6. **Inferential and Sequential – "Therefore," "Thus," or "Moreover":** In a logical or explanatory context, *atha* serves as a linguistic marker to infer consequences, continue arguments, or elaborate upon previous statements. Its presence enhances the sense of sequence, causality, or forward motion in a dialogue or treatise.
7. **Implying Doubt or Command:** Though not as commonly noted, *atha* can reflect uncertainty or command, depending on its placement within a sentence. It may carry undertones of hesitation, suggestion, or authority.

Kara: The word *kara* in Sanskrit, though seemingly concise, unfolds a wealth of meanings shaped by its wide-ranging applications across various disciplines like language, poetry, and philosophy. Rooted in the concept of "*karoti*" (one who does, makes, or causes), *kara* can take on concrete, symbolic, and abstract connotations depending on its context. It most commonly surfaces as a **suffix** or **standalone noun**, adding flexibility to its interpretation and enriching Sanskrit's expressive scope.

1. "Hand" – The Literal and Figurative Limb

One of the most fundamental meanings of *kara* is "hand"—a symbol of human agency, capability, and action. The hand is emblematic of not just physical gestures but also metaphorical creation and productivity. For instance, the poet Kālidāsa in his works brings out sensuous elegance with vivid imagery of hands engaged in love or ritual. In contexts describing *kāma* (love) or daily action, the hand performs divine and poetic functions, such as holding flowers, grasping an object of beauty, or conducting rituals.

2. "A Ray of Light" – The Illuminating Beam

Symbolically extending beyond the physical world, *kara* is also used to describe a **ray of light** or a radiant beam. Here, *kara* connects the human domain to celestial beauty, often depicted poetically to invoke dawn's glow, sunbeams, or moon rays filtering through vast spaces. For example, a metaphorical description such as "*alambita-karah*" brings alive imagery where the Sun's rays seem as though they physically uplift a divine entity. This meaning lends the term an ethereal, abstract charm while reinforcing its association with brilliance and illumination.

3. "The Elephant's Trunk" – Symbol of Strength

In classical Sanskrit literature, *kara* finds a striking representation as the **trunk of an elephant**—an emblem of extraordinary power and grace. An elephant’s trunk serves as both a functional appendage and a regal ornament, inspiring poetic descriptions in epics and plays. Whether portrayed lifting water droplets (*sīkarī*), scattering flowers, or uprooting trees, *kara* in this sense underlines nature's strength and majesty.

4. "Tax, Toll, or Tribute" – Acts of Sovereignty

The word *kara* also extends to the administrative realm as it refers to **taxes, tolls, or tributes** levied by kings and rulers. This definition features prominently in treatises on governance and epics that depict political conquests. Sovereigns collecting *kara* from subordinate states or citizens demonstrates authority and hierarchical order. In poetic works, this taxation imagery often merges with light, where the Sun is imagined as exacting tolls (rays) over earth's vast surface.

5. Hail – A Natural Occurrence

Another notable use of *kara* emerges in meteorological contexts to signify **hail**, blending its meanings between elements of force and purity. Hailstorms bring both destructive intensity and renewal, reinforcing the term’s dual attributes of power and natural rhythm.

6. A Measure of Length

In a technical and practical sense, *kara* also specifies a unit of measurement, equivalent to **24 thumbs**. This precise application exemplifies the term's role in describing standardized measurements in architecture and crafts.

7. Symbolic Meanings

Beyond its tangible meanings, *kara* conveys broader ideas as:

- **A Means or Expedient:** A solution or tool that enables action or achievement.
- **A Doer or Performer:** Reflecting the essence of action embodied in the term’s root "*karoti*" (one who performs).

Narrative Description of the Term "Kāra"

Closely related but nuanced in its application, *kāra* serves as a suffix and standalone word to denote action, effort, creation, and sound. When paired with specific roots or concepts, *kāra* becomes an agentive force, highlighting the individual or mechanism involved in acts of craftsmanship, labor, or speech.

1. A Creator or Doer

In compounds, *kāra* translates to "maker" or "doer." For instance:

- **Granthakāraḥ:** Author of a text.
- **Kumbhakāraḥ:** A potter.

- **Suvarṇakārah:** A goldsmith.
These terms celebrate craftsmanship, creative authorship, and industry, which are cornerstones of human effort.

2. Act or Action

As a standalone noun, *kāra* simply means an **act or action**, exemplified in concepts like *puruṣakāra* (man's effort or exertion). This aligns *kāra* with human determination and industriousness, emphasizing self-effort as a transformative force.

3. Exertion and Determination

Kāra reflects **effort, strength, or determination**, often embodying the toil behind achievements, whether physical or intellectual.

4. Sound and Speech

Linguistically, *kāra* also signifies a **non-inflected sound or letter**. Words like *akāra* , the "a" sound) demonstrate this usage, celebrating Sanskrit's structural precision in articulating sounds.

5. Strength, Religious Austerity, and Husband

- **Power and Strength:** In its profound sense, *kāra* denotes **power** or innate **strength**, underscoring resilience or valor.
- **Religious Austerity:** Actions born of ascetic discipline—whether spiritual, physical, or ethical—are encapsulated by *kāra*.
- **A Husband or Lord:** In metaphorical relationships, *kāra* refers to a protector, master, or husband, establishing bonds of care or authority.

Other Meanings

- **Female Messenger:** A woman tasked with delivering messages, often in the context of political or amorous relationships.
- **Female Worker in Gold:** A craftswoman skilled in artistry.

24-The Inscribed Texts on Seal H-92

Figure:29

Table:28

P- 04	P- 87	P- 58	P- 60	P- 104	P- 127	P- 150	Pati ksha atha
Pati	ksh	atha	s	kka	a	ṇ	sakka ṇa

Kṣa:The Sanskrit letter *Kṣa* , though a single syllable, holds deep symbolic and lexical significance within both linguistic and cultural traditions. Rooted in ancient texts, epics, and lexicons, *Kṣa* weaves together meanings that span destruction, protection, divine incarnations, and natural phenomena. Its complexity and layers of meaning make it a unique and multidimensional term that reflects the dual nature of creation and dissolution in the universe.

1. **Kṣa as the Symbol of "Kṣatriya"**

One of the most fundamental and notable meanings of *Kṣa* is "**Kṣatriya**," the warrior class within the four-fold division of Indian society (*Varṇa*). Kṣatriyas symbolize protection, valor, and leadership, tasked with upholding justice and societal order. Here, *Kṣa* aligns with concepts of governance, power, and duty—marking its role as a protector and preserver of Dharma.

2. **"Field" – The Space of Production and War**

In another sense, *Kṣa* refers to a **field** (*kṣetra*), which is simultaneously a place of cultivation and warfare. The field embodies two contrasting yet intertwined ideas: the fertility and growth associated with agriculture and the battleground that hosts conflict, loss, and heroism. This dual meaning reflects life's perpetual cycle of creation and destruction.

3. **"Narasimha" – The Divine Lion-Man Incarnation**

Kṣa holds significant theological importance as it represents **Narasimha**, the third incarnation of Lord Viṣṇu. In the Narasimha Avatar, Viṣṇu manifests in a fierce form with a lion's head and a human body to destroy the demon Hiraṇyakaśipu and protect his devotee Prahlāda. This association with Narasimha emphasizes the righteous destruction of evil and divine intervention to restore balance and justice.

4. "Hari (Viṣṇu)" – The Protector and Sustainer

Hari, another epithet for Lord Viṣṇu, is also encapsulated within the symbol *Kṣa*. As Viṣṇu, the cosmic protector, *Kṣa* conveys divine sustenance and preservation. Here, the term shifts from the ferocity of Narasimha to the serene, nurturing form of Viṣṇu, reinforcing its connection to protection, harmony, and spiritual refuge.

5. "Protector of Temples and Gatekeeper"

In a more practical and societal sense, *Kṣa* extends to represent **guardians of temples** and **gatekeepers**. Such figures are charged with ensuring the sanctity and security of sacred spaces, preventing the intrusion of impurity. This reinforces *Kṣa*'s association with roles of safeguarding and maintaining order.

6. "Lightning" – A Symbol of Force and Transience

On a natural level, *Kṣa* symbolizes **lightning**, the transient and destructive power of nature. Lightning reflects both awe-inspiring beauty and untamable energy, serving as a metaphor for sudden change or divine wrath. Within this meaning, *Kṣa* embodies momentary destruction but also illumination, hinting at forces beyond human control.

7. "Destruction and Loss" – The Ultimate Dissolution

Kṣa is synonymous with **destruction**, **loss**, or the dissolution of the world (*Pralaya*). Rooted in the verb *kṣi* or *kṣai*, meaning "to waste" or "decay," the term captures the inexorable passage of time that leads to disappearance and end. Whether it represents physical destruction or metaphysical dissolution, *Kṣa* serves as a reminder of impermanence—echoing the cyclical nature of existence in Indian philosophy.

8. "Demon and Goblin" – Agents of Destruction

In mythological contexts, *Kṣa* also denotes a **demon or goblin**, forces often depicted as agents of chaos and darkness. Demons symbolize obstacles to righteousness and represent the untamed, destructive forces of the universe. As entities to be subdued or overcome, they reflect the cosmic struggle between good and evil.

9. "Loss and Disappearance"

Related to destruction, *Kṣa* additionally signifies **loss** and **disappearance**, extending its symbolism from physical ruin to abstract notions of fading away—be it material possessions, time, or spiritual ignorance. This reinforces its connection to endings and transformations.

The Sanskrit root *Utthā*, arising from the combination of *ud* (up) and *sthā* (to stand), holds a versatile and dynamic range of meanings across physical, mental, and metaphorical dimensions. Its essence embodies ideas of rising, striving, originating, and awakening, capturing the spirit of both literal and symbolic elevation. Across classical Sanskrit texts, *Utthā* conveys themes of action, renewal, and courage—integral qualities of movement and progress in various contexts.

1. The Literal Act of Rising and Standing

At its core, *Utthā* represents the simple yet profound act of **standing up or rising**. Whether in a physical sense of standing after rest, awakening from slumber, or moving toward an upright posture, the term marks the commencement of activity. For example, in *Manusmṛti* (2.194) and the epic Rāmāyaṇa (9.59), *utthā* conveys the action of getting up—either to perform a duty or engage in an important pursuit.

In poetic expressions like Kalidasa’s *Raghuvamśa* or Bhāravi’s *Kirātārjunīya*, rising often signals readiness for heroic deeds, affirming one’s resolve or confronting life’s challenges.

2. Departure, Cessation, or Giving Up

Utthā also implies the act of **departing from, giving up, or ceasing** something. In contexts such as giving up penance, fasting, or inactivity, the word denotes intentional movement away from a state of rest or stagnation. For example:

- "An individual rises (*uttiṣṭhati*) after fasting" (*Pañcatantra*). This nuance emphasizes progress, renewal, or intentional transformation toward a higher state of being.

3. Rising of Natural Phenomena – Sun, Life, and Effort

The term extends beyond human action to describe natural occurrences where the **sun rises, light emerges, or life springs forth**. It can reflect celestial bodies, waves on water, and natural energies awakening. Expressions such as "*Karābhighātōthita kanduka*" evoke vivid images like a ball rebounding when struck, capturing motion and vitality.

Similarly, *utthā* symbolizes life’s resurgence, such as rebounding after death or awakening after sleep. Kalidasa’s verses refer to such motions as manifestations of vigor or divine resurgence (*Kumārasambhava* 7.4).

▪ Originating, Springing Forth, or Arising

Another deeply symbolic meaning of *Utthā* is **originating or springing forth**. It refers to something emerging, accruing, or bursting into being. This can apply to:

- **Sounds** of applause (*Daśakumāracharita* 49), spontaneously rising as expressions of admiration.
- **Wealth or consequence** generated from a field, town, or people, e.g., “A hundred arise from the village” (*Mahābhārata*).

- **Ideas, emotions, or power** that well up spontaneously (*Bhavatsaṃbhāvanottha*, emotions rising from recognition).

5. Strengthening, Growth, and Struggle

In a broader context, *utthā* reflects an increase in **strength, power, or opposition**. Enemies, diseases, or challenges may *rise* or *grow*, prompting either vigilance or struggle. It underscores the dynamic nature of life where forces—both constructive and destructive—arise and require response. For example, “One must not ignore an enemy that is rising in strength” (*Śiśupālavadhā* 2.1). This growth is not restricted to negativity; it also represents self-improvement, effort, and the courage to act: “*Uttiṣṭhamānaṃ mitrārthe*”—“Who would not value a friend making efforts for your cause?” (*Bhaṭṭikāvya* 8.12).

6. To Become Brave, Active, or Enthusiastic

At its most inspirational, *utthā* captures the essence of **rising above challenges** with bravery, determination, and effort. Whether it is a soldier on the battlefield, a friend striving for another's welfare, or an individual awakening to higher goals, *utthā* champions resilience and movement.

- “*Hṛdayadaurbalyaṃ tyaktvā uttiṣṭha*”—“Rise, relinquishing faint-heartedness” (*Bhagavad Gītā* 2.3).

7. Revival, Awakening, and Making Efforts (Causative Form: Utthāpayati)

The causative form, *utthāpayati*, conveys actions like **raising someone or something up, reviving life, or instigating effort**:

1. **Raising up**—To lift objects or inspire people (*R.* 14.59).
2. **Reviving life**—Arousing someone from death or awakening hidden potential (*Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa*).
3. **Inciting action**—Encouraging individuals to act with resolve or bravery (*Śiśupālavadhā* 2.12).

Additionally, the causative meaning incorporates offering **support, aid, or nourishment**, thus tying *utthā* to compassion and collective strength.

8. The Concept of Uttha – That Which Springs Forth

As an adjective and suffix, *Uttha* signifies **arising, produced, or originating** from something. It conveys origins and generation:

- “*Samīraṇottha*” (arising from the wind).
- “*Ānandottha*” (arising from joy).

Symbolic and Metaphorical Meanings of Na

Beyond grammatical transformations, *Na* assumes multiple symbolic meanings in broader Sanskrit literature. While rare as the starting point of words, it denotes diverse concepts across realms of knowledge, spirituality, and human behavior.

1. **Knowledge and Certainty:**

In its most abstract sense, *Ṇa* symbolizes **knowledge, certainty, and ascertainment**—attributes tied to clarity and understanding. It reflects the unwavering nature of realized truth, affirming intellect and confidence.

2. **Adornment and Beauty:**

As an ornament (*bhūṣaṇa*), *Ṇa* signifies decoration, embellishment, or that which enhances beauty—whether physical, spiritual, or intellectual. An ornament here transcends materiality and can represent qualities that adorn one's character, such as knowledge or virtue.

3. **A Water or Summer-House:**

The term finds expression in architecture and leisure, symbolizing a **water-house or summer pavilion** designed for coolness, comfort, and repose. It connects to serenity—a refuge where body and spirit rejuvenate.

4. **A Bad Man:**

Interestingly, *Ṇa* also connotes a **bad or wicked person**, juxtaposing its auspicious meanings. This dual association might reflect the paradox of human nature and speech—both tools of creation and potential discord.

5. **Śiva – The Divine:**

In spiritual contexts, *Ṇa* assumes divine significance as a name of **Śiva**, the transformative deity of the Hindu pantheon. As *Ṇa* is phonetically potent, representing sound vibration and negation, it aligns perfectly with Śiva, who embodies both dissolution and transcendence.

6. **Negation or Denial:**

As a representation of **negation** (*nāda*), *Ṇa* signifies the sound or vibration of denial. This usage finds roots in early Vedic and linguistic traditions where phonemes acquire meanings reflecting cosmic principles.

7. **Gift and Generosity:**

The syllable resonates with the concept of **giving and generosity**, suggesting an act of offering that stems from abundance, kindness, or spiritual fulfillment.

25-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-1150

Figure:30

Table:29

P-270	P-189	P-60	P-72	P-127	P-242	Ni ṭha sa śa
ni	ṭh	s	ś	a	āehh	āehha

Iha: "Here" and "This World"

The Sanskrit word *Iha* is primarily an **adverb** and refers to space, time, or existence, carrying the subtle yet profound nuance of "here" and "in this world."

1. Spatial Usage—'Here'

In spatial contexts, *Iha* refers to the present or immediate location.

- Example: (*nehābhikramanāśo'sti*, Bhagavad Gita 2.40)—“Here, no effort is ever lost.” In this famous spiritual context, *Iha* transcends a literal spatial meaning and aligns more with the present moment as a domain of moral or spiritual action.

2. Temporal Usage—'Now or at this Time'

"Iha" also denotes the "present time" as distinct from the past (*paratra*) or other dimensions of existence:

- *Iha-paratra śuddhida* from the *Jñānārṇava* signifies the concept of "purity in both worlds," meaning in *this life* and the *hereafter*—an essential theme in Jain and Hindu ethics.

3. Existential or Philosophical Usage—'In This World'

Philosophically, *Iha* contrasts with concepts like *paratra* (the other world or the hereafter). It often signifies our physical or earthly existence, where karma operates and liberation is sought.

- Jain, Buddhist, and Hindu texts consistently frame *Iha* as the plane of action (karma-bhūmi).

In its essence, *Iha* invites introspection on the **present moment** and life's role in larger cosmic frameworks.

Īhā: "Effort, Desire, or Endeavor"

Īhā stems from the root *īh* (to strive or wish) and holds a more active, intentional connotation—centered on the interplay of **effort, desire, and action**.

1. Desire and Intention

At its root, *Īhā* represents **wish** or **intention**—the precursor to effort. Examples include desires arising from passion or ambition:

- (*hantuṃ krodhavaśādīhāṃ cakrāte nau parasparam, Kumārasambhava 7.53*)
“Overcome by anger, they directed their intent (toward slaying one another).”

2. Effort or Activity

When elevated beyond intention, *Īhā* emphasizes active effort or determination:

- (*prajāgarāṃcakārārēhāsvanīśamādarāt, Bhaṭṭikāvya*)—"He exerted sleepless effort against his enemies with utmost diligence." Such usage ties *Īhā* with **perseverance** and disciplined activity—qualities central to spiritual, moral, or worldly accomplishment.

3. Undertaking or Action

As an extension of effort, *Īhā* also refers to undertakings or acts driven by resolve:

- (*īhātaśceddhanam bhavet, Manusmṛti 9.25*)—"Wealth comes by effort." This reflects the Sanskrit worldview of aligning intent, action, and outcomes.

26-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-1146

Figure:31

Table:30

𑀧𑀸	𑀧𑀸𑀓	𑀧𑀸	𑀧𑀸𑀓𑀧𑀸
P-311	P- 105	P-70	Pā Lkka sha
Pā	lkk	sh	

Semantic Analysis of *Pālaka*

The term *Pālaka* originates from the root **pāl** (*to protect, guard*) and signifies a protector, guardian, or ruler. The word is both a **noun** and an **adjective**, contextually implying roles of care, supervision, sovereignty, and maintenance.

1. General Meanings of *Pālaka*

The Sanskrit texts illustrate the multifaceted usage of *Pālaka* in secular and spiritual domains:

a. Guardian or Protector

Pālaka commonly refers to one who **protects** or **guards**, aligning it closely with themes of care and responsibility.

- **Buddhist and Pali context** (*pālaka*): “a guard, keeper, or protector.”
- **Śivapurāṇa**: *Pālaka* is associated with Karttikeya as the divine **protectorate of the universe** (*brahmāṇḍasyāsi pālakah*).

Here, *Pālaka* implies a cosmic guardian, demonstrating the protector's divine function on a universal scale.

b. Prince, King, or Sovereign

In royal or administrative contexts, *Pālaka* signifies a king, ruler, or sovereign charged with the protection of his subjects:

- **Kathāsaritsāgara:** *Pālaka* refers to a prince, as seen in the mention of the two sons *Pālaka* and *Gopālaka*, born to King Caṇḍamahāsenā and Aṅgāravatī.

In this sense, *Pālaka* highlights **leadership rooted in protection and maintenance**, which is an essential dharma (duty) for a king in classical Indian literature.

c. Maintenance, Observance, and Foster Care

Pālaka also extends to maintaining or observing promises, vows, or responsibilities, showcasing trustworthiness:

- "One who maintains or observes (as a promise or custom)."

Philosophical and Cultural Reflections

1. Duties of Kingship:

A ruler (*pālaka*) must serve as the **custodian of dharma**, ensuring justice, protection, and welfare for his subjects. In classical texts, a *pālaka* reflects the ideal of a **kṣatriya king**, who embodies strength and responsibility.

2. Divine Protection:

The Śivapurāṇa emphasizes divine beings (e.g., *Karttikeya*) as *pālakas* who guard cosmic balance. This connects human rulers to celestial roles of protection.

3. Daily Roles:

From the occupational (horsekeeper) to familial (foster father), *Pālaka* applies to tangible, earthly guardians, extending the theme of protection into relatable, practical scenarios.

4. Ethical Undertones:

A *pālaka* also represents **moral guardianship**—upholding promises, principles, or commitments, which is integral to dharmic living.

Semantic Analysis of *Ṣa*

The term *Ṣa* is a Sanskrit noun and adjective with significant, multi-layered meanings. Its roots reflect themes of **excellence, destruction, loss, and liberation**. Context determines whether *Ṣa* applies to earthly, intellectual, or spiritual planes.

1. Grammatical Overview

- **Category:** Adjective (*ṣaḥ*, *ṣā*, *ṣam*) and Noun (masculine/neuter).
- **Root:** Likely derived from **ṣo** (*to destroy, end, or reduce*), with suffixes *-kaṃ* or *-da*.

2. Primary Meanings and Contextual Nuances

a. Adjective: “Best, Excellent”

As an adjective, *ṣa* signifies **excellence**, superiority, or outstanding qualities. For instance:

- *Ṣaḥ vidvān* – an **excellent teacher** or a distinguished learned man.

3. Symbolic Reflections

1. Loss and Liberation:

The overlapping meanings of *loss*, *destruction*, and *liberation (mokṣa)* emphasize the transience of material reality. Loss leads to **detachment** and, eventually, eternal bliss.

2. Excellence and Wisdom:

As the *best* or *excellent* (particularly applied to teachers or learned individuals), *ṣa* underscores the value placed on knowledge and those who safeguard it.

3. End as Transformation:

“End” does not merely signify cessation; it indicates transition—such as the transition to **mokṣa** or a higher, peaceful state.

4. Sleep and Eternal Rest:

Sleep (*nidra*) symbolizes temporary respite, while eternal rest (*heaven, mokṣa*) signifies freedom from **saṃsāra** (the cycle of life and death).

5. Embryo as Origin:

Ṣam as **embryo** connects themes of beginnings and creation with endurance, reflecting **cyclic existence**.

27-The Inscribed Texts on Seal M-1157

Figure:32

Table:31

𑀓	𑀧𑀭	𑀧	𑀓	𑀓𑀧𑀭𑀓
P-189	P-311	P-283	P-60	ṭha Pā u sa
ṭh	Pā	u	s	

Semantic Analysis of *Uṣa* and *Uṣā*

The terms *Uṣa* and *Uṣā* are linked through themes of **light, transformation, and renewal**, associated with early morning (dawn) and metaphorically symbolizing awakening, rebirth, and fertility.

- **Dawn** symbolizes transformation—a **fresh start** filled with hope after darkness. It also reflects spiritual enlightenment (*jñāna-dīpti*).
- **Libidinous tendencies** represent primal or passionate urges that arise with the renewal of nature in the early morning.

1. *Uṣā* as a Goddess:

- Personifies dawn, illuminating the world after night.
- Praised in the **R̥gveda** for dispelling darkness and awakening life, associated with **divine beauty** and **grace**.

2. *Uṣā*, daughter of *Bāṇa* (mythology):

- **Role:** A key figure in Hindu mythology, *Uṣā*'s story represents love, longing, and divine union.

28- The Inscribed Texts on Seal H-591

Figure:33

Table:32

𑀓	(𑀘)		𑀕𑀺	𑀓(𑀘) 𑀕𑀺
P-107	P-77	P-147	P-313	Ka khari a apā
k	khri	a	apā	

Khari : Core Meanings and Interpretations

1. Divine Entities

- **A semi-divine female able to fly:**
 - Often linked to beings with **supernatural abilities** such as the *Vidyadhari*s or celestial nymphs (*apsaras*).
 - This resonates with the concept of higher realms, divine beauty, and otherworldly powers.
- **An epithet of Durgā:**
 - As an aspect of **Goddess Durgā**, *Khari* signifies her **transcendental power** to rise above worldly limitations, akin to flying.
 - It emphasizes Durgā's protective and liberating aspects, symbolizing her control over the elements (*śakti*).

2. Magical and Yogic Connotations

- **The magical power of flying (*siddhi*):**
 - Flying (*Khecari Siddhi*) represents the ability to transcend physical boundaries and attain freedom.

- Yogic texts (e.g., *Haṭha Yoga Pradīpikā*) identify *Khecarī Mudrā* as a crucial practice for achieving this siddhi.
- **Khecarī Mudrā (particular position of fingers):**
 - A yogic practice involving positioning the tongue or fingers to **channel energy** upward through the body.
 - It is associated with **kundalini awakening**, inner flight (spiritual ascension), and immortality.

"A" : Symbolism and Key Meanings

1. Universal Significance

- **Primordial Sound:** In **Vedic philosophy**, *A* is considered the first manifestation of sound and **existence** itself. It symbolizes:
 - The source of **creation** (*Ādi*—beginning).
 - **Brahmā**, who initiates the creation of the universe.
- **Spiritual Connotation:**
 - *A* is the opening sound in the **Praṇava (Om)** mantra: *A-U-M*, which signifies the cycle of creation, preservation, and destruction (symbolic of **Brahmā, Viṣṇu, and Śiva**).

2. Lexical Meanings

According to classical sources like *Nānārtharatnamālā*:

- **Deities:** *A* signifies **Brahmā, Viṣṇu, Śiva, and Pārvatī**—highlighting its association with divinity and the universal forces of creation and destruction.
- **Battle (*Yuddha*):** Symbolizes **conflict** and the **cosmic struggle** between dharma and adharma.
- **Female apartments (*Antaḥpura*):** Reflects themes of domesticity, intimacy, and sacred feminine spaces.
- **Flame (*Agni*):** Symbolizing **purity**, energy, and **transformation**.
- **Mantra:** A **powerful vibrational tool** in ritual practices, embodying cosmic sounds.

Combined Significance

1. Divinity and Transcendence:

- Both *Kharī* and *A* reflect the **divine power to transcend limits**: *Kharī* through flight (*siddhi*), and *A* through its primal connection to sound, creation, and spirituality.

2. Energy and Transformation:

- *Kharī*'s link to Durgā emphasizes transformative **Śakti energy**, while *A* represents **Agni** (flame), the fuel for both physical and spiritual transformation.

3. Creation and Renewal:

- As the first letter, *A* is foundational to language, representing the genesis of thought and communication.
- *Kharī* symbolizes freedom and divine grace, offering a path of renewal and transcendence.

29-The Inscribed Texts on Seal K-40

Figure:34

The interpretation was abandoned due to ambiguity in the initial sign encountered from left to right

Conclusive note: This paper has endeavored to explore potential entries for understanding the possible meaning and interpretation of the Indus Texts. It is hoped that this work will garner the attention of scholars. The validation and further suggestions from Sanskrit scholars are crucial. Their insights will significantly contribute to a more definitive attempt at deciphering the Indus Script and resolving the enduring enigma surrounding this period in both Indian and world history.

Encouraged by the results and outcomes of this preliminary research, I anticipate collaboration for further investigation within a suitable Sanskrit institution. I am confident that this approach will yield fruitful results.

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